

Austria

TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZOONOSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS IN FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS

including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria
and some pathogenic microbiological agents

IN 2017

PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC*. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2017.

The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and indicator bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks.

Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given. The information given covers both zoonoses that are important for the public health in the whole European Union as well as zoonoses, which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the European Union legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual European Union Summary Reports on zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance that are published each year by EFSA.

The national report contains two parts: tables summarising data reported in the Data Collection Framework and the related text forms. The text forms were sent by email as pdf files and they are incorporated at the end of the report.

* Directive 2003/ 99/ EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2003 on the monitoring of zoonoses and zoonotic agents, amending Decision 90/ 424/ EEC and repealing Council Directive 92/ 117/ EEC, OJ L 325, 17.11.2003, p. 31

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ANIMAL POPULATION TABLES

Table Susceptible animal population

Animal species	Category of animals	Population			
		holding	animal	slaughter animal (heads)	herd/flock
Cattle (bovine animals)	Cattle (bovine animals)	60,675	1,957,196	678,258	
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	55,626	627,894	56,288	
Deer	Deer - farmed	1,981	46,167		
Gallus gallus (fowl)	Gallus gallus (fowl)			83,835,000	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	65	983,761		123
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	16	251,037		34
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	605	69,141,179		5,088
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	1,119	9,845,089		2,880
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	65	983,761		123
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	16	251,037		34
Goats	Goats	10,431	109,486	44,258	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	10,105	73,330	11,341	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	4,458	36,156	32,917	
Pigs	Pigs	30,048	2,870,096	5,152,595	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	5,417	240,755	84,881	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	22,743	1,083,881	5,067,714	
Rabbits	Rabbits	5,408	45,201		
Sheep	Sheep	17,241	456,978	244,676	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	16,123	260,892	60,766	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	13,630	196,086	183,910	
Solipeds, domestic	Solipeds, domestic	18,370	90,993	546	
Turkeys	Turkeys	151	2,065,594		444
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	151	2,065,594		444
Wild boars	Wild boars - farmed	5	1,129		

DISEASE STATUS TABLES

Table Bovine brucellosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme

Region	Number of animals serologically tested under investigations of suspect cases	Number of suspended herds under investigations of suspect cases	Number of seropositive animals under investigations of suspect cases	Number of animals positive to BST under investigations of suspect cases	Number of animals positive in microbiological testing under investigations of suspect cases	Number of herds with status officially free	Number of infected herds	Total number of animals	Number of herds tested under surveillance	Number of animals tested under surveillance	Total number of herds	Number of infected herds tested under surveillance	Number of herds tested under surveillance by bulk milk	Number of animals or pools tested under surveillance by bulk milk	Number of infected herds tested under surveillance by bulk milk	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of Brucella infections	Number of abortions due to Brucella abortus	Number of animals tested by microbiology under investigations of suspect cases
AUSTRIA	514	8	0	0	0	60,675	0	1,957,196	1,295	10,952	60,675	0	1,324	1,324	0	357	0	0	193

Table Ovine or Caprine brucellosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme

Region	Number of animals serologically tested under investigations of suspect cases	Number of suspended herds under investigations of suspect cases	Number of seropositive animals under investigations of suspect cases	Number of animals positive in microbiological testing under investigations of suspect cases	Number of herds with status officially free	Number of infected herds	Total number of animals	Number of herds tested under surveillance	Number of animals tested under surveillance	Total number of herds	Number of infected herds tested under surveillance	Number of animals tested by microbiology under investigations of suspect cases
AUSTRIA	49	2	0	0	24,556	0	566,464	1,591	19,503	24,556	0	3

DISEASE STATUS TABLES

Table Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme

Region	Number of herds with status officially free	Number of infected herds	Total number of animals	Interval between routine tuberculin tests	Number of animals tested with tuberculin routine testing	Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination	Total number of herds
AUSTRIA	60,667	8	1,957,196	0	17,699	8	17	9	60,675

PREVALENCE TABLES

Table Campylobacter:CAMPYLOBACTER in food

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Bakery products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Bakery products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Chocolate - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	6	0	Campylobacter	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	3	0	Campylobacter	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	21	14	Campylobacter coli Campylobacter jejuni	1 13
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter coli	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	54	35	Campylobacter	2
								Campylobacter coli	6
								Campylobacter jejuni	27
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	10	6	Campylobacter coli	2
								Campylobacter jejuni	4
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	2	Campylobacter jejuni	2
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	2	Campylobacter coli	2
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	35	18	Campylobacter	14
								Campylobacter jejuni	4
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	6	4	Campylobacter	4
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	6	2	Campylobacter	2
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	8	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from duck - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	3	3	Campylobacter	3
	Meat from duck - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	3	2	Campylobacter jejuni	2
						21	17	Campylobacter	17
	Meat from geese - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter	1
	Meat from geese - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
						21	10	Campylobacter	10
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	3	3	Campylobacter coli	1
								Campylobacter jejuni	2
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	5	4	Campylobacter coli	2
								Campylobacter jejuni	2

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	2	Campylobacter coli	1
								Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter coli	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	16	10	Campylobacter jejuni	10
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	44	18	Campylobacter	3
								Campylobacter coli	5
								Campylobacter jejuni	10
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	10	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from spent hens (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	2	Campylobacter	2
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	6	3	Campylobacter coli	2
								Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	34	13	Campylobacter	5
								Campylobacter coli	3
								Campylobacter jejuni	5
						69	30	Campylobacter	30
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	12	1	Campylobacter coli	1
								Campylobacter	15
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	18	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	17	8	Campylobacter	8
	Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	4	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	13	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	8	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	17	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Mushrooms - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	5	0	Campylobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	4	0	Campylobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Other products of animal origin - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter jejuni	1
	Other products of animal origin - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	1	Campylobacter coli	1
	Ready-to-eat salads - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Sauce and dressings - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Vegetables - pre-cut - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Vegetables - products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	2	0	Campylobacter	0
	Vegetables - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter	1	0	Campylobacter	0

Table Cronobacter:CRONOBACTER in food

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Infant formula - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	2	0	Cronobacter	0
	Infant formula - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	2	0	Cronobacter	0
	Infant formula - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	3	0	Cronobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	1	0	Cronobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	20	0	Cronobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	14	0	Cronobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	2	0	Cronobacter	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 22964:2017 Cronobacter	2	0	Cronobacter	0

Table Escherichia coli:ESCHERICHIA COLI in food

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Bakery products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Bakery products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	15	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	14	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
		25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	10	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0	

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
		25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0	
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	11	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
		25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0	
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	7	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	17	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Chocolate - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	34	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	10	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	6	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Fruits - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Juice - fruit juice - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	20	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	65	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	6	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	1	VTEC O146	H21	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eee negative	1
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	7	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
		25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	6	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0	
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	14	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	31	1	VTEC O174	H2	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified ;VT1, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	17	6	VTEC O146	H-	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									H28	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									VTEC O153	H25	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	17	6	VTEC Orough	H28	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									Hrough	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	2	VTEC O142	H16	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									VTEC Orough	H-	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	20	3	VTEC Orough	H-	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									H11	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									H28	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									Hrough	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	1	VTEC O6	H10	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	15	2	VTEC O148	H48	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
									VTEC Orough	H21	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	1	VTEC O54	H-	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	6	1	VTEC O146	H28	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eee negative	1
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	16	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	15	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	9	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	8	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from pig - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	7	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Border inspection activities - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Processing plant - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat from sheep - meat preparation - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from sheep - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	1	VTEC O181	H49	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified; VT1, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	10	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild game - birds - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat from wild game - birds - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	4	1	VTEC O54	H-	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	10	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	58	1	VTEC, unspecified	Not Available	Verotoxin production, toxin type unknown	Adhesion genes investigation not reported	1
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	42	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	33	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	10	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	41	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
		25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	3	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0	
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	10	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	44	2	VTEC Orough	H4	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	2
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	12	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
		25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0	
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	15	1	VTEC Orough	H25	VT2, gene identified, subtype unspecified ;VT1, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eae negative	1

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	8	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	17	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Mushrooms - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	6	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	9	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
			25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Other products of animal origin - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	1	VTEC O78	H-	VT1, gene identified, subtype unspecified	eee negative	1
	Ready-to-eat salads - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Sauce and dressings - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - non-pre-cut - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - pre-cut - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxin genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Area of sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	total units tested	total units positive	Zoonoses	ANTH	VTX	AG	N units positive
Not Available	Vegetables - products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	8	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	5	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	1	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0
	Vegetables - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)	2	0	Verocytotoxi genic E. coli (VTEC)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	0

Table FLAVIVIRUS in animal

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Vaccination status	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Birds - pet animals - Unspecified - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	animal	Not Available	PCR	1	1	West Nile virus	1
	Birds - wild - Conservation facilities - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	animal	Not Available	PCR	9	9	West Nile virus	9
	Birds - wild - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	animal	Not Available	PCR	119	2	West Nile virus	2
	Solipeds, domestic - horses - Farm - Austria - animal sample - blood - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	animal	Unknown	Seroneutralisation test	2	2	West Nile virus	2
	Solipeds, domestic - horses - Farm - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	animal	Unknown	Real-Time PCR (qualitative or quantitative)	6	1	West Nile virus	1

Table HISTAMINE in food

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Beverages, alcoholic - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	51	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	1
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
	Beverages, alcoholic - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	3	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	1
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
	Beverages, alcoholic - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Beverages, alcoholic - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Beverages, alcoholic - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
	Beverages, non-alcoholic - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	1	1	> 400	Histamine	0	1
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	15	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200	Histamine	0	1
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	20	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200	Histamine	0	0
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	28	2	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200	Histamine	0	2
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	10	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200	Histamine	0	1
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	1	1	> 400	Histamine	0	1
							>200 TO <= 400	Histamine	0	0
							<=200	Histamine	0	0
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	6	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200 TO <= 400	Histamine	0	1
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200 TO <= 400	Histamine	0	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	9	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200 TO <= 400	Histamine	0	0
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	16	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	0
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200 TO <= 400	Histamine	0	1
	Fish - raw - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fish - raw - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	11	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	10	1	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
							> 400	Histamine	0	1
							>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0
							>200 TO <= 400	Histamine	0	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Histamine	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	1	> 400	Histamine	0	1	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	10	Gram	1	0	>100 TO <= 200	Histamine	0	0	

Table LISTERIA in food

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Bakery products - bread - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - bread - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	15	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	15	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	15	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	15	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	15	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	51	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	50	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	50	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	51	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	51	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - desserts - containing raw cream - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - desserts - containing raw cream - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	29	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	29	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	29	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	29	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	29	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Bakery products - pastry - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	98	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	96	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	96	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	98	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	98	1
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	28	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	28	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	28	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	15	1

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	1
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	15	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	15	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	15	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	25	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	25	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	27	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	27	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	41	1
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	41	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	43	1
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	42	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	42	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	43	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	50	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	49	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	49	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	50	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	50	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	11	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	11	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	11	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	11	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Crustaceans - shrimps - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Crustaceans - shrimps - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	12	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	36	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	36	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	36	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	36	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	36	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - buttermilk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - chocolate milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Border inspection activities - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Border inspection activities - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - made from pasteurised milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	11	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	11	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	11	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	26	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	26	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	25	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	22	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	22	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	25	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	27	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	27	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	27	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	40	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	40	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	62	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	62	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	62	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	92	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	68	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	68	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	92	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	33	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	7	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Egg products - dried - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Egg products - dried - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Egg products - liquid - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Egg products - liquid - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Egg products - liquid - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Egg products - liquid - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Egg products - liquid - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Egg products - liquid - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - gravad /slightly salted - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - gravad /slightly salted - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - marinated - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - marinated - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
					6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
					6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
					9	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
					9	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
	Fish - raw - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	16	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	16	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	16	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Fish - raw - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	16	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	16	0
	Fish - raw - frozen - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	1
	Fish - raw - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - raw - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - raw - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	13	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	13	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	13	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - raw - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	24	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	24	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Fruits - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fruits - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Fruits - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Infant formula - ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	17	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	17	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	17	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	15	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	15	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	15	1
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	2	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	9	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	2	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	9	2
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	1
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - chilled - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - chilled - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - chilled - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	1
	Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	1
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	1

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	1
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	5	2	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	5	2	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	2
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	1
	Meat from pig - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	14	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	14	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	14	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	79	3	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	79	3
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - chilled - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - sliced - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	12	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	12	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	51	2	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	51	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	51	1
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	51	2	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	51	2
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	1
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	44	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	42	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	42	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	44	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	44	1
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	42	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	42	5	>100	Listeria monocytogenes	42	1
							detection	Listeria monocytogenes	42	5
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	34	3
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	34	3	>100	Listeria monocytogenes	34	0	
						detection	Listeria monocytogenes	34	3	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	10	2	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0	
						>100	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	10	2	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	10	2	
						<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0	
						detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0	
						>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0	

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	10	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	10	1
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	58	2	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	58	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	58	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	58	2	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	58	2
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	54	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	53	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	53	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	54	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	52	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	12	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	12	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	12	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	11	1
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	10	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	10	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
	Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	18	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	16	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	16	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	18	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	18	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Milk, sheep's - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Molluscan shellfish - cooked - frozen - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	1
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sandwiches - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	6	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	1
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	57	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	45	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	45	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	57	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	39	1
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Catering - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	7	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	114	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	114	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive		
Not Available	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	182	3	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	85	0		
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	85	0		
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	182	3	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	182	3		
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0		
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0		
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0		
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	39	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	39	0		
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	39	0		
							104	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	104	0
									>100	Listeria monocytogenes	104	0
							203	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	98	0
									>100	Listeria monocytogenes	98	1
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	39	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	39	0		
							104	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	104	0
							203	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	181	1
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	25	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0		
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0		
							26	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	26	0
									>100	Listeria monocytogenes	26	0
							88	3	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	61	0
									>100	Listeria monocytogenes	61	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	25	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	25	0		
							26	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	26	0
							88	3	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	83	3
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0		
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0		
							3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
									>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							9	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
									>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
					3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
					9	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
					6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
					7	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	7	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
					6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
					7	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	3	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	6	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	3	0
>100							Listeria monocytogenes	3	0	
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	6	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0	
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0	
						>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0	
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	8	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	8	0	
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	5	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0	
						>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0	
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	5	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	5	0	
Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0	

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Method	Zoonoses	N of units tested	N of units positive
Not Available	Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
Vegetables - pre-cut - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
Vegetables - products - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	2	0
	Vegetables - products - Catering - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
Vegetables - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	1	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	6	0
	Vegetables - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	1	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	6	1
Vegetables - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	10	0
Vegetables - products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	4	0
Vegetables - products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
Vegetables - products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	<= 100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
							>100	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0
	Vegetables - products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	detection	Listeria monocytogenes	1	0

Table Lyssavirus:LYSSAVIRUS in animal

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Method	Sampling unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Alpine chamois - Hunting - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	3	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Badgers - wild - Hunting - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	4	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Badgers - wild - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Official sampling - Selective sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	8	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Bats - wild - Unspecified - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Selective sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	94	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Bats - wild - Unspecified - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	5	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Cats - pet animals - Unspecified - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	23	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified - Farm - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	4	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Deer - wild - roe deer - Hunting - Austria - animal sample - brain - Unspecified - Not applicable - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	2	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Dogs - pet animals - Unspecified - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	18	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Foxes - wild - Hunting - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	94	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Foxes - wild - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Official sampling - Selective sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	79	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Marten - wild - Hunting - Austria - animal sample - brain - Unspecified - Not applicable - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	8	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Raccoons - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - brain - Monitoring - passive - Official sampling - Selective sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	1	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Rodents - pet animal - Unspecified - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Not applicable - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	1	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Rodents - wild - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - brain - Unspecified - Not applicable - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	4	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Sheep - Farm - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	1	0	Lyssavirus	0
	Solipeds, domestic - horses - Farm - Austria - animal sample - brain - Clinical investigations - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	Indirect Immunofluorescent Antibody test (IFAT)	animal	3	0	Lyssavirus	0

Table Salmonella:SALMONELLA in animal

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	N of flocks under control programme	Target verification	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	5088	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5024	180	Salmonella Bovismorbificans	5
								Salmonella Coeln	3
								Salmonella Enteritidis PT 6c	1
								Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	2
								Salmonella group C1	3
								Salmonella Havana	3
								Salmonella Infantis	114
								Salmonella Livingstone	6
								Salmonella Manhattan	2
								Salmonella Mbandaka	6
								Salmonella Moero	8
								Salmonella Montevideo	6
								Salmonella Senftenberg	4
Salmonella Thompson	18								
Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	5088	Y	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5088	183	Salmonella Bovismorbificans	5	
							Salmonella Coeln	3	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 6c	1	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	2	
							Salmonella group C1	3	
							Salmonella Havana	3	
							Salmonella Infantis	117	
							Salmonella Livingstone	6	
							Salmonella Manhattan	2	
							Salmonella Mbandaka	6	
							Salmonella Moero	8	
							Salmonella Montevideo	6	
							Salmonella Senftenberg	4	
Salmonella Thompson	18								
Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Objective sampling	herd/flock	5088	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	66	3	Salmonella Infantis	3	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	2880	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2613	14	Salmonella Enteritidis PT 23	1	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 5	1	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	3	
							Salmonella Enteritidis RDNC	1	
							Salmonella Indiana	2	
							Salmonella Java	1	
							Salmonella Mbandaka	2	
							Salmonella Thompson	2	
							Salmonella Typhimurium DT 120	1	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	2880	Y	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2880	33	Salmonella Coeln	2	
							Salmonella enterica, subspecies diarizonae	2	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 1	1	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 23	3	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 4	1	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 5	1	
							Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	5	
							Salmonella Enteritidis RDNC	4	
							Salmonella Indiana	2	
							Salmonella Infantis	1	
							Salmonella Java	1	
							Salmonella Mbandaka	3	
							Salmonella Montevideo	2	
Salmonella Szentes	1								

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	N of flocks under control programme	Target verification	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	2880	Y	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2880	33	Salmonella Thompson	3
								Salmonella Typhimurium DT 120	1
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Objective sampling	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Objective sampling	herd/flock	2880	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1731	19	Salmonella Coeln	2
								Salmonella enterica, subspecies diarizonae	2
								Salmonella Enteritidis PT 1	1
								Salmonella Enteritidis PT 23	2
								Salmonella Enteritidis PT 4	1
								Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	2
								Salmonella Enteritidis RDNC	3
								Salmonella Infantis	1
								Salmonella Mbandaka	1
								Salmonella Montevideo	2
								Salmonella Szentes	1
Salmonella Thompson	1								
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Suspect sampling	herd/flock	2880	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	2	Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	2	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens - during rearing period - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	433	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	433	0	Salmonella	0	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	123	Y	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	123	3	Salmonella Infantis	2
								Salmonella Thompson	1
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line - during rearing period - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	61	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	61	1	Salmonella Infantis	1	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line - adult - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	34	Y	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	34	0	Salmonella	0	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line - during rearing period - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	15	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	15	0	Salmonella	0	
Turkeys - fattening flocks - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Industry sampling - Census	Turkeys - fattening flocks - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	444	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	429	10	Salmonella Anatum	1
								Salmonella Coeln	3
								Salmonella Manhattan	4
								Salmonella Mbandaka	1
								Salmonella Stanley	1
Turkeys - fattening flocks - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	Turkeys - fattening flocks - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official and industry sampling - Census	herd/flock	444	Y	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	444	12	Salmonella Anatum	1
								Salmonella Coeln	5
								Salmonella Manhattan	4
								Salmonella Mbandaka	1
								Salmonella Stanley	1
Turkeys - fattening flocks - before slaughter - Farm - Austria - environmental sample - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Objective sampling	herd/flock	444	N	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	23	2	Salmonella Coeln	2	

Table Salmonella:SALMONELLA in food

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Bakery products - bread - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - cakes - containing raw cream - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	22	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	70	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - cakes - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	30	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	112	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - pastry - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	13	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	18	0	Salmonella	0
	Bakery products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Beverages, non-alcoholic - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Beverages, non-alcoholic - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Cereals and meals - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	18	0	Salmonella	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	12	0	Salmonella	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	21	0	Salmonella	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Chocolate - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Chocolate - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Packing centre - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	22	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	43	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	31	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Crustaceans - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - shrimps - raw - frozen - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - shrimps - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - shrimps - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	35	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Border inspection activities - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	41	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	354	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Processing plant - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	136	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	172	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	18	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - dried - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - dried - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - liquid - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - liquid - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - liquid - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - liquid - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - liquid - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - liquid - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - Packing centre - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Egg products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	13	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Egg products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Eggs - raw material (liquid egg) for egg products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Eggs - table eggs - Packing centre - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
240			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0	
300			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	24	0	Salmonella	0	
360			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0	
	Eggs - table eggs - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
300			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0	
	Eggs - table eggs - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Eggs - table eggs - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Eggs - table eggs - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
240			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0	
300			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	35	0	Salmonella	0	
360			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0	
	Eggs - table eggs - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Eggs - table eggs - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Eggs - table eggs - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fats and oils (excluding butter) - fats - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	14	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	19	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	28	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - gravad /slightly salted - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	16	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - raw - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - smoked - cold-smoked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - smoked - hot-smoked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - smoked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fish - unspecified - chilled - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	8	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Fishery products, unspecified - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - smoked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - non-pre-cut - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - pre-cut - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - dried - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - dried - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	17	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	22	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - products - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Fruits - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Fruits - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - dried - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	8	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	15	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Infant formula - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - pasteurised - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	20	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - fruit juice - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/food)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Juice - mixed juice - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - mixed juice - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - mixed juice - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Juice - mixed juice - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	17	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	37	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten raw - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	1	Salmonella Derby	1
								Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - carcass - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - carcass - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - neck skin - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - HACCP and own check - Objective sampling	slaughter animal batch	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	194	50	Salmonella Agona	4
								Salmonella Bredeney	1
								Salmonella Coeln	1

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - carcass - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - neck skin - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - HACCP and own check - Objective sampling	slaughter animal batch	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	194	50	Salmonella Infantis	34
								Salmonella Montevideo	9
								Salmonella Thompson	3
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	21	3	Salmonella Infantis	3
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica rough	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	2	Salmonella Infantis	2
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	58	7	Salmonella Infantis	7
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	25	2	Salmonella Infantis	2
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	3	Salmonella Infantis	3
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	2	Salmonella Infantis	2
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
25			Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0	
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from duck - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from duck - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	1	Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	1
21						2	Salmonella group C2	1	
							Salmonella Typhimurium DT 193	1	
	Meat from geese - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from geese - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Typhimurium 193	1
21						4	Salmonella Newport	3	
							Salmonella Typhimurium DT 8	1	
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	15	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	15	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
			10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	1	Salmonella Newport	1
	Meat from other animal species or not specified - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from pig - carcass - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - carcass swabs - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - HACCP and own check - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	100	Square centimetre	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5557	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - fresh - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
			10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	29	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
			10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
			10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	97	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	19	0	Salmonella	0
			10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeding)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from pig - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	2	Salmonella Infantis	2
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	39	5	Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica rough	1
								Salmonella Infantis	3
								Salmonella Stanley	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	63	10	Salmonella Agona	1
								Salmonella Hadar	2
								Salmonella I 4,12,27:b:-	1
								Salmonella Infantis	6
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	15	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Hadar	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from sheep - fresh - Border inspection activities - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from sheep - meat preparation - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from sheep - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from spent hens (Gallus gallus) - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from turkey - carcass - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - neck skin - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - HACCP and own check - Objective sampling	slaughter animal batch	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	89	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	37	4	Salmonella Bredeney	1
Salmonella Coeln								2	
Salmonella Typhimurium DT 12								1	
Salmonella Bredeney								1	
Salmonella Saintpaul								1	
						82	2		
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	14	0	Salmonella	0
Salmonella Derby								1	
Salmonella Hadar								2	
Salmonella Typhimurium DT 104I								1	
						48	4		
	Meat from turkey - fresh - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	16	1	Salmonella Kentucky	1
	Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	2	Salmonella Derby Salmonella Typhimurium DT 104I	1 1
	Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from wild boar - fresh - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from wild boar - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat from wild game - birds - fresh - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	25	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	81	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Slaughterhouse - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - fresh - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Game handling establishment - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Cutting plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	47	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	33	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	39	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	21	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
			25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	42	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	11	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	10	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Farm - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feeder)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	8	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	17	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, goats' - raw milk - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Milk, sheep's - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Molluscan shellfish - shelled, shucked and cooked - frozen - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Mushrooms - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Mushrooms - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Mushrooms - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Processing plant - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	34	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	53	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	35	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - roasted - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Nuts and nut products - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Nuts and nut products - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	17	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Other food - Processing plant - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Processing plant - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	18	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	25	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Other food of non-animal origin - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Packing centre - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	65	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	30	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	13	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	66	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	252	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	145	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - based on Regulation 2073 - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Other products of animal origin - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other products of animal origin - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Ready-to-eat salads - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	27	0	Salmonella	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	39	0	Salmonella	0
	Ready-to-eat salads - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	8	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Sauce and dressings - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	28	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	8	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, dried - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Seeds, sprouted - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Soups - dehydrated - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - dried - Farm - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - dried - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - dried - Processing plant - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - dried - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - dried - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Packing centre - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	31	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Processing plant - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Processing plant - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	19	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	19	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Spices and herbs - Wholesale - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Sweets - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Sweets - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Sweets - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - bean - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - pre-cut - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - products - Processing plant - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	10	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - products - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - products - Wholesale - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Vegetables - Wholesale - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0

Table Salmonella:SALMONELLA in feed

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Complementary feedingstuffs - final product - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Complementary feedingstuffs - final product - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Complementary feedingstuffs - final product - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Complementary feedingstuffs - final product - Retail - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Complementary feedingstuffs - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Complementary feedingstuffs - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - pelleted - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - pelleted - Retail - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - pelleted - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - pelleted - Retail - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - pelleted - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed d)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens - final product - pelleted - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens - final product - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens - final product - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - pelleted - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for sheep - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for sheep - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - barley derived - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - maize derived - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - maize derived - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	8	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - by-products of brewing and distilling - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - by-products of brewing and distilling - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - by-products of brewing and distilling - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - wheat derived - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of cereal grain origin - wheat derived - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Feed material of land animal origin - protein meal - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal - Retail - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	2	Salmonella Bredenezy Salmonella Lexington	1 1
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived - Farm - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	1	Salmonella Cerro	1
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	12	2	Salmonella Derby Salmonella Mbandaka	1 1
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other feed material - miscellaneous - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other feed material - other plants - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Other feed material - other plants - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other feed material - tubers, roots and similar products - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Other feed material - tubers, roots and similar products - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Other feed material - tubers, roots and similar products - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Other feed material - tubers, roots and similar products - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones) - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	9	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	3	1	Salmonella Derby	1
								Salmonella Infantis	1
	Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones) - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	1	Salmonella Derby	1
		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones) - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	4	0	Salmonella	0
		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	1	Salmonella Derby	1
								Salmonella Livingstone	1
							Salmonella London	1	
	Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones) - Retail - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones) - Retail - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	1	Salmonella Coeln	1
	Pet food - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	1	Salmonella Infantis	1
	Pet food - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - final product - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	7	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - Retail - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	6	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - Retail - Non European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Pet food - Retail - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	2	0	Salmonella	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Pet food - rodents - Processing plant - European Union - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Premixtures - process control - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	5	0	Salmonella	0
	Premixtures - process control - non-pelleted/meal - Processing plant - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Premixtures - process control - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Austria - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0
	Premixtures - process control - non-pelleted/meal - Retail - Unknown - feed sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella	1	0	Salmonella	0

Table Toxoplasma:TOXOPLASMA in animal

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Method	Sampling unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified - Farm - Austria - animal sample - blood - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Latex agglutination test (LAT)	animal	28	0	Toxoplasma	0
	Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified - Farm - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Real-Time PCR (qualitative or quantitative)	animal	2	0	Toxoplasma	0
	Foxes - wild - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Real-Time PCR (qualitative or quantitative)	animal	1	0	Toxoplasma	0
	Goats - Farm - Austria - animal sample - blood - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Latex agglutination test (LAT)	animal	26	17	Toxoplasma gondii	17
	Goats - Farm - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Real-Time PCR (qualitative or quantitative)	animal	24	1	Toxoplasma gondii	1
	Hares - wild - Natural habitat - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Real-Time PCR (qualitative or quantitative)	animal	1	1	Toxoplasma gondii	1
	Pigs - Farm - Austria - animal sample - blood - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Latex agglutination test (LAT)	animal	1	1	Toxoplasma gondii	1
	Sheep - Farm - Austria - animal sample - blood - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Latex agglutination test (LAT)	animal	22	12	Toxoplasma gondii	12
	Sheep - Farm - Austria - animal sample - organ/tissue - Monitoring - passive - Not applicable - Not specified	Real-Time PCR (qualitative or quantitative)	animal	35	2	Toxoplasma gondii	2

Table Trichinella:TRICHINELLA in animal

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Method	Sampling unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Badgers - wild - Hunting - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Not applicable - Not specified	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	7	0	Trichinella	0
	Foxes - wild - Hunting - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Not applicable - Not specified	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	11	0	Trichinella	0
	Pigs - breeding animals - not raised under controlled housing conditions - boars - Slaughterhouse - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Census	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	1384	0	Trichinella	0
	Pigs - breeding animals - not raised under controlled housing conditions - sows - Slaughterhouse - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Census	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	84410	0	Trichinella	0
	Pigs - fattening pigs - not raised under controlled housing conditions - Slaughterhouse - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Census	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	50382 13	0	Trichinella	0
	Solipeds, domestic - horses - Slaughterhouse - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Census	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	546	0	Trichinella	0
	Wild boars - farmed - Slaughterhouse - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Census	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	1544	0	Trichinella	0
	Wild boars - wild - Slaughterhouse - Unknown - animal sample - organ/tissue - Control and eradication programmes - Official sampling - Census	Magnetic stirrer method for pooled sample digestion	animal	22769	0	Trichinella	0

Table Yersinia:YERSINIA in food

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Bakery products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Bakery products - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	2	0	Yersinia	0
	Cereals and meals - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	2	0	Yersinia	0
	Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Chocolate - Retail - Unknown - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Fishery products, unspecified - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	6	0	Yersinia	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	3	0	Yersinia	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	2	0	Yersinia	0
	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	5	0	Yersinia	0
	Meat from pig - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Mushrooms - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta - Retail - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	4	0	Yersinia	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Sauce and dressings - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Seeds, dried - Retail - Non European Union - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Vegetables - pre-cut - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/fee d)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	2	0	Yersinia	0

Area of Sampling	Matrix - Sampling stage - Sampling origin - Sample type - Sampling context - Sampler - Sampling strategy	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight unit	Method	Total units tested	Total units positive	Zoonoses	N of units positive
Not Available	Vegetables - products - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0
	Vegetables - Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service - Austria - food sample - Surveillance - Official sampling - Objective sampling	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica	1	0	Yersinia	0

FOODBORNE OUTBREAKS TABLES

Foodborne Outbreaks: summarized data

Causative agent	Food vehicle	Outbreak strenght		Strong				Weak			
				N		N		N			
		N outbreaks	N human cases	hospitalized	N deaths	N outbreaks	N human cases	hospitalized	N deaths		
Campylobacter coli	Unknown					2	4	1	0		
Campylobacter jejuni	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof					3	6	1	0		
	Fish and fish products					1	2	0	0		
	Fruit, berries and juices and other products thereof					1	2	1	0		
	Unknown					14	40	9	0		
Campylobacter, unspecified sp.	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof					1	3	1	0		
	Unknown					2	4	0	0		
Clostridium botulinum	Pig meat and products thereof	1	2	2	0						
	Unknown					1	2	2	0		
Enteropathogenic E. coli (EPEC)	Unknown					1	2	0	0		
Hepatitis A	Crustaceans, shellfish, molluscs and products thereof					1	2	0	0		
Listeria monocytogenes - molecular serogroup IIa	Meat and meat products	1	7	7	1						
Listeria monocytogenes - serovar 4b	Vegetables and juices and other products thereof	1	2	2	1						
Norovirus	Fish and fish products	1	17	0	0						
	Mixed food					1	5	1	0		
Salmonella Agona	Unknown					1	4	0	0		
Salmonella Arechavaleta	Sweets and chocolate					1	2	0	0		
Salmonella Dublin	Cheese	1	4	1	0						
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 1	Unknown					1	2	0	0		
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 11	Eggs and egg products					1	2	2	0		
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 13a	Unknown					1	2	0	0		
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 21	Eggs and egg products	1	7	3	0						
	Unknown					1	2	0	0		
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 4	Unknown					1	2	0	0		
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	Eggs and egg products	2	8	1	0	2	4	2	0		
	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof					1	3	1	0		
	Buffet meals	1	6	3	0						
	Unknown					9	41	4	0		
Salmonella Paratyphi A	Unknown					1	2	2	0		
Salmonella Poona	Unknown					1	2	1	0		
Salmonella Typhimurium DT 120	Unknown					1	3	1	0		
Salmonella Typhimurium DT 7a	Unknown					2	4	2	0		
Salmonella Typhimurium RDNC	Unknown					1	2	1	0		
Salmonella Typhimurium U 311	Unknown					1	2	1	0		
Salmonella Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	Unknown					1	2	0	0		

Causative agent	Food vehicle	Outbreak strenght							
		Strong				Weak			
		N outbreaks	N human cases	N hospitalized	N deaths	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hospitalized	N deaths
VTEC O103	Unknown					1	2	0	0
VTEC O157	Unknown					2	12	0	0
VTEC O26	Unknown					2	7	4	0

Strong Foodborne Outbreaks: detailed data

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths
Clostridium botulinum	Not Available	4839	Household	Pig meat and products thereof	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household	Household	Austria	Unknown	N_A	1	2	2	0
Listeria monocytogenes - molecular serogroup IIa	Not Available	Meta 42	General	Meat and meat products	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Multiple places of exposure in one country	Processing plant	Austria	Cross-contamination	N_A	1	7	7	1
Listeria monocytogenes - serovar 4b	Not Available	Meta 41	General	Vegetables and juices and other products thereof	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Unknown	Farm	European Union	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient; Inadequate heat treatment	N_A	1	2	2	1
Norovirus	Not Available	4700	General	Fish and fish products	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Hospital or medical care facility	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	17	0	0
Salmonella Dublin	Not Available	4542	General	Cheese	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Farm	Farm	Austria	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient; Inadequate heat treatment	N_A	1	4	1	0

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 21	Not Available	4476, 4478	Household	Eggs and egg products	N_A	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service; Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	7	3	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	Not Available	4504	Household	Eggs and egg products	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household	Household	Austria	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4594	General	Buffet meals	N_A	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Austria	Unknown	N_A	1	6	3	0
		4633	General	Eggs and egg products	N_A	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans; Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	Austria	Not Available	N_A	1	6	1	0

Weak Foodborne Outbreaks: detailed data

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths
Campylobacter coli	Not Available	4474	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4602	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
Campylobacter jejuni	Not Available	4384	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4393	Household	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4438	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Household	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4450	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Canteen or workplace catering	School or kindergarten	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	11	0	0
		4472	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4480	Household	Fish and fish products	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4498	Household	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4510	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4512	Household	Fruit, berries and juices and other products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	European Union	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4525	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Others	Unknown	Not Available	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4528	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
4532	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not Available	N_A	1	3	0	0		
4580	Household	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0	

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths	
Campylobacter jejuni	Not Available	4584	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	2	0	
		4586	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	3	0	0	
		4628	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4658	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	Not Available	N_A	1	2	2	0
		4675	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	2	0
		4712	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Take-away or fast-food outlet; Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	3	0	0
Campylobacter, unspecified sp.	Not Available	4530	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Not Available	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0	
		4610	General	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	3	1	0	
		4612	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Unknown	Not Available	N_A	1	2	0	0
Clostridium botulinum	Not Available	4537	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	2	0	
Enteropathogenic E. coli (EPEC)	Not Available	4694	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0	
Hepatitis A	Not Available	4526	General	Crustaceans, shellfish, molluscs and products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	Unknown	Not Available	N_A	1	2	0	0	

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths
Norovirus	Not Available	4565	General	Mixed food	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	5	1	0
Salmonella Agona	Not Available	4553	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Other contributory factor	N_A	1	4	0	0
Salmonella Arechavaleta	Not Available	4592	General	Sweets and chocolate	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Household	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 1	Not Available	4709	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 11	Not Available	4615	Household	Eggs and egg products	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Austria	Inadequate heat treatment	N_A	1	2	2	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 13a	Not Available	4419	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 21	Not Available	4623	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Not Available	N_A	1	2	0	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 4	Not Available	4488	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	Not Available	4443	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Other contributory factor	N_A	1	3	0	0
		4451	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Canteen or workplace catering	School or kindergarten	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	11	0	0
		4481	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths	
Salmonella Enteritidis PT 8	Not Available	4496	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0	
		4513	Household	Eggs and egg products	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Unknown	Inadequate heat treatment	N_A	1	2	2	0	
		4534	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Household	Household	Austria	Unknown	N_A	1	3	0	0	
		4603	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0	
		4609	General	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Not Available	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	3	1	0
		4679	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
		4722	Household	Eggs and egg products	N_A	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4723	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Canteen or workplace catering	Canteen or workplace catering	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	11	0	0
		Meta 40	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	5	1	0
Salmonella Paratyphi A	Not Available	4502	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	2	0	
Salmonella Poona	Not Available	4514	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0	
Salmonella Typhimurium DT 120	Not Available	4505	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	3	1	0	
Salmonella Typhimurium DT 7a	Not Available	4381	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0	
		4635	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0	

Causative agent	Other Causative Agent	FBO nat. code	Outbreak type	Food vehicle	More food vehicle info	Nature of evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of food vehicle	Contributory factors	Comment	N outbreaks	N human cases	N hosp.	N deaths
Salmonella Typhimurium RDNC	Not Available	4506	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
Salmonella Typhimurium U 311	Not Available	4511	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	1	0
Salmonella Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	Not Available	4590	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	2	0	0
VTEC O103	Not Available	4527	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Other contributory factor	N_A	1	2	0	0
VTEC O157	Not Available	4562	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Other contributory factor	N_A	1	2	0	0
		4620	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	10	0	0
VTEC O26	Not Available	4508	Household	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Household	Unknown	Other contributory factor	N_A	1	3	0	0
		4731	General	Unknown	N_A	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	N_A	1	4	4	0

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE TABLES FOR CAMPYLOBACTER

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline	
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2	
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5	
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64	
N of tested isolates	8	8	8	8	8	8	
MIC	N of resistant isolates	4	0	0	4	1	6
<=0.12	2						
0.25	1		3				
<=0.5						2	
0.5	1		5				
<=1		6					
1					3		
2		2			4		
4				1			
8	3			3			
16	1						
>16					1		
>64				4		6	

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	3	3	3	3	3	3
MIC	N of resistant isolates	3	0	0	3	2
<=0.12			1			
0.25			1			
<=0.5						1
0.5			1			
<=1		2				
1					2	
2		1				
4						1
8	2					
16	1				1	
>64				3		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Poland

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
N of resistant isolates	2	0	0	2	1	1
MIC						
0.25			1			
<=0.5						1
0.5			1			
<=1		2				
2					1	
8	2					
16					1	
64				1		
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Unknown

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
N of resistant isolates	2	0	0	2	0	2
MIC						
0.25			2			
<=1		2				
1					1	
2					1	
8	1					
16	1					
>64				2		2

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Czech Republic

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	1
0.25			1			
<=1		1				
16	1					
>16					1	
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Germany

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
0.5			1			
<=1		1				
1					1	
16	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Croatia

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0	0
MIC						
0.25			1			
<=0.5						1
<=1		1				
1					1	
8	1					
>64				1		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Hungary

	AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
	ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
	Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
	Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
	N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
MIC	N of resistant isolates	2	0	0	2	0	0
	<=0.5						2
	0.5			2			
	<=1		1				
	1					1	
	2		1			1	
	8	1					
	16	1					
	>64				2		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Italy

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	3	3	3	3	3	3
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
<=0.12	2					
0.25			3			
<=0.5						2
<=1		1				
1					3	
2		1				
4		1		2		
16	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	11	11	11	11	11	11
MIC	N of resistant isolates	9	1	0	9	2
0.25	2		4			
<=0.5						3
0.5			6			
<=1		8				
1			1		5	
2		1			4	
4	1	1				
8	3			1		
16	4			1		
>16	1				2	
>64				9		8
>128		1				

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0	1
MIC						
0.25			1			
<=1		1				
1					1	
8	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Germany

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0	0
MIC						
0.25			1			
<=0.5						1
<=1		1				
1					1	
8	1					
>64				1		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Hungary

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
0.25			1			
1					1	
2		1				
16	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Hungary

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0	1
MIC						
0.25			1			
<=1		1				
1					1	
8	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - frozen

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	4	4	4	4	4	4
MIC	N of resistant isolates	3	0	0	3	2
<=0.12	1					
0.25			1			
<=0.5						2
0.5			3			
<=1		3				
1					2	
2		1				
8	2			1		
16	1				1	
>16					1	
>64				3		2

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - frozen

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	8	2	16	4	2
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
0.25			1			
<=1		1				
1					1	
16	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline	
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1	
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5	
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64	
N of tested isolates	44	44	44	44	44	44	
MIC	N of resistant isolates	36	0	0	35	1	23
<=0.12	8		24				
0.25			19				
<=0.5						17	
0.5			1		22		
<=1		43					
1					20	4	
2		1			1		
4				7			
8	25			2			
16	5				1		
>16	6						
>64				35		23	

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	7	7	7	7	7	7
MIC	N of resistant isolates	4	0	0	3	3
<=0.12	2		3			
0.25	1		3			
<=0.5						4
0.5			1		2	
<=1		5				
1					3	
2		2			1	
4				2		1
8	2			2		
16	2					
>16					1	
>64				3		2

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Slovenia

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
<=0.12	1		2			
<=0.25					1	
<=0.5						2
<=1		2				
1					1	
2				1		
8	1					
>64				1		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Unknown

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
0.5			1			
<=1		1				
1					1	
8	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Germany

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
N of resistant isolates	0	0	0	0	0	0
MIC						
<=0.12	1					
<=0.5						1
0.5			1			
<=1		1				
2					1	
8				1		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Hungary

	AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
	ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
	Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
	Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
	N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
MIC	N of resistant isolates	2	0	0	2	0	0
	0.25			1			
	<=0.5						2
	0.5			1		1	
	<=1		2				
	1					1	
	8	2					
	>64				2		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Hungary

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
N of resistant isolates	2	0	0	2	0	1
MIC						
<=0.12			1			
0.25			1			
<=0.5						1
0.5					1	
<=1		2				
1					1	
4	1					
16	1					
>64				2		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	3	3	3	3	3	3
N of resistant isolates	3	0	0	3	1	1
MIC						
<=0.12			1			
0.25			1			
<=0.5						2
0.5			1		1	
<=1		2				
1					1	
2		1				
8	2					
16	1					
>16					1	
>64				3		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	20	20	20	20	20	20
MIC	N of resistant isolates	9	0	0	9	0
<=0.12	10		6			
0.25	1		12			
<=0.5						13
0.5			2		4	
<=1		14				
1					15	
2		6			1	
4				7		
8	5			4		
16	2					
>16	2					
>64				9		7

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Poland

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
<=0.12			1			
1					1	
2		1				
8	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Unknown

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0	0
MIC						
0.25			1			
<=0.5						1
1					1	
2		1				
16	1					
>64				1		

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Germany

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	4	4	4	4	4	4
MIC	N of resistant isolates	3	0	0	3	0
<=0.12	1		2			
0.25			1			
<=0.5						3
0.5			1		2	
<=1		2				
1					1	
2		2			1	
4				1		
8	1					
16	2					
>64				3		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from turkey - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Hungary

AM substance	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	1	1	1	1	1	1
MIC	N of resistant isolates	1	0	0	1	0
0.25			1			
1					1	
2		1				
8	1					
>64				1		1

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - frozen

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
AM substance						
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	13	13	13	13	13	13
MIC	N of resistant isolates					
	9	0	0	8	0	5
<=0.12	4		8			
<=0.25					1	
0.25			4			
<=0.5						7
0.5			1		6	
<=1		9				
1					6	1
2		3		1		
4		1		3		
8	2					
16	4			1		
>16	3					
32						1
>64				8		4

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - frozen

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Suspect sampling

Programme Code: OTHER AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

	Ciprofloxacin	Erythromycin	Gentamicin	Nalidixic acid	Streptomycin	Tetracycline
AM substance						
ECOFF	0.5	4	2	16	4	1
Lowest limit	0.12	1	0.12	1	0.25	0.5
Highest limit	16	128	16	64	16	64
N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2
N of resistant isolates	2	0	0	2	0	1
MIC						
0.25			2			
<=0.5						1
<=1		2				
1					2	
8	2					
>64				2		1

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE TABLES FOR SALMONELLA

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE TABLES FOR INDICATOR ESCHERICHIA COLI

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Meat from bovine animals - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON pnI2

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
N of resistant isolates	5	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0
MIC										
<=0.015							4			
<=0.03									5	
0.03							1			
<=0.064			3							
<=0.12						2		3		
0.12			2							
0.25						3		2		
1					2					
2					1					1
4	2			3	2					2
8	1			2						2
16		1								
32	2	1								

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
N of resistant isolates	5	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0
MIC										
64		1								
>64		2								

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Meat from bovine animals - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
N of resistant isolates	5	0	5	5	0	1	0	0	0	1	3	3	0	3
MIC														
<=0.015						2								
<=0.03									5					
0.03						2								
<=0.25													5	
<=0.5								5						
<=1							5							
1				2										2
<=2		1										2		
2				2										
<=4										4				
4		2												
>4			5											
<=8					5						1			
8		2		1		1								
>32														3
64											1	2		
>64	5											1		
>128										1				
>1024											3			

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: AMR MON pn12

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
N of resistant isolates	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MIC										
<=0.015							2			
<=0.03									2	
<=0.064			2							
<=0.12						2		2		
<=0.25					2					
0.5	1	2								
1	1									
2										1
4				1						1
8				1						

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim		
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2		
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25		
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32		
N of tested isolates	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181		
N of resistant isolates	16	0	2	0	11	7	0	1	0	5	32	44	0	13		
MIC																
<=0.015						159										
<=0.03										178						
0.03						14										
0.064						1										
0.12						1										
<=0.25			179										178	77		
0.25						2										
<=0.5				181					150							
0.5			2			2							3	65		
<=1							181									
1								30								
<=2			11										105			
2	41															
<=4										173						
4	118	67												29	2	
<=8					157						34					
8	6	99				2							3			
16			4			13				1	1	84				
32					1							31				
>32														11		
64										2						18
>64	16													26		
128					6						1					

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181
N of resistant isolates	16	0	2	0	11	7	0	1	0	5	32	44	0	13
MIC														
>128					4					2				
1024											1			
>1024											31			

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON pnI2

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid		Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid		Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68
N of resistant isolates	63	68	7	7	6	67	7	7	1	0	0	0
MIC												
<=0.015										58		
<=0.03											67	
0.03											6	
<=0.064	1	55										
0.064										3	1	
<=0.12							28	1	52			
0.12	4	6										
0.25	2							30	15			
0.5	1	1		1	1		2	1				
1	1	1	4		6							
2	1	4			1	20	1	5				
4	14	2			38	20	1				31	
8	32	1	1		23	14						33
16	8	5			1	7						4
32	4	21			1							
64	27				3							

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin		
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Negative/Absent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available		
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Negative/Absent	Not Available	Not Available		
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68
N of resistant isolates	63	68	7	7	6	67	7	7	1	0	0	0
MIC >64		7			1							

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68
N of resistant isolates	68	4	68	67	12	30	0	7	0	18	43	41	0	36
MIC														
<=0.015						36								
<=0.03										67				
0.03						1								
0.064						1								
0.12										1				
<=0.25											62	11		
0.25						9								
<=0.5				1					51					
0.5						8							6	19
<=1							67							
1			2	10				9						2
<=2												25		
2			4	19			1	1	1					
<=4										43				
4			33	1	18								2	
>4				61										
<=8					54							6		
8			26	13				6						
>8				7			6							
16			3				2			1	13			
32								4						
>32									2					
64			3				3					2	13	

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68
N of resistant isolates	68	4	68	67	12	30	0	7	0	18	43	41	0	36
MIC														
>64	68	1										28		
128					3					2				
>128					6					14				
>1024											43			

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Pigs - fattening pigs

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: AMR MON pn12

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid		Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid		Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
N of resistant isolates	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	0	0	0	0
MIC												
<=0.015										2		
<=0.03											3	
<=0.064			2									
0.064										1		
<=0.12							2					2
0.25	1											
0.5										1		
2	1					2						
4					2							
8	1			1				1				
16			2									
32			1									
>64					1							

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Pigs - fattening pigs

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: AMR MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim	
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2	
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25	
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32	
N of tested isolates	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	
N of resistant isolates	36	1	3	3	6	7	0	3	0	5	44	73	0	23	
MIC															
<=0.015						150									
<=0.03										180					
0.03						23									
<=0.25			177								168	54			
0.25						3									
<=0.5				177					143						
0.5						4								12	89
<=1	3							180							
1				1					34						
<=2			5								81				
2	37				1										
<=4										172					
4	96	75													
>4			3												
<=8					166						33				
8	8	94					2				3	2			
>8				1									2		
16			5				8			1	66	2			
32					2						33	1			
>32					1									23	
64					1						1	4	26		
>64	36	1													
128					1						2				

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180
N of resistant isolates	36	1	3	3	6	7	0	3	0	5	44	73	0	23
MIC														
>128					2					2				
>1024											44			

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Pigs - fattening pigs

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON pn12

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid		Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid		Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181
N of resistant isolates	175	181	10	10	12	178	10	10	0	0	0	0
MIC												
<=0.015										148		
<=0.03											180	
0.03											30	
<=0.064	1	157										
0.064										3	1	
<=0.12							81	2	136			
0.12	5	12										
0.25	3	2						78	4	45		
0.5	5						3	5	1			
1	9	1	4		29							
2	8	2	2		6	75	1		7			
4	38	14	3		95	40	5		72			
8	69	8				68	23	4		96		
16	34	22	1		2	9	6					
32	8	53				3	2					
>32	1											

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin		
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Negative/Absent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available		
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Negative/Absent	Not Available	Not Available		
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181
N of resistant isolates	175	181	10	10	12	178	10	10	0	0	0	0
MIC												
64		61			4							
>64		20			3							

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Pigs - fattening pigs

Sampling Stage: Slaughterhouse

Sampling Type: animal sample - caecum

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim	
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2	
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25	
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32	
N of tested isolates	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	
N of resistant isolates	181	4	181	178	16	42	0	5	0	35	111	104	0	103	
MIC															
<=0.015						126									
<=0.03										180					
0.03						10									
0.064						3									
<=0.25													172	33	
0.25						7									
<=0.5					3										
0.5						7									
<=1							179								
1			1	41			2				35				
<=2			3										69		
2			4	67			2			4					
<=4											138				
4			90	15	44			1							8
>4				161											
<=8					157						25				
8			83	17			8				6				
>8				9											
16			1			8				2	2	38			
32			1			2			1	1	7	1			
>32								2							
64			1			5				2					
>64	181	2													

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181
N of resistant isolates	181	4	181	178	16	42	0	5	0	35	111	104	0	103
MIC														
128					4					3				
>128					5					29				
256											1			
>1024											110			

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Meat from pig - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON pn12

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid		Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid		Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin
	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Negative/Abs ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29
N of resistant isolates	26	29	4	4	6	29	4	4	0	0	0	0
MIC												
<=0.015										24		
<=0.03											28	
0.03										3		
<=0.064			21									
0.064										2	1	
<=0.12							14			21		
0.12	3	4										
0.25	1							8	8			
0.5	1				1			3				
1	2				2	5		1				
2	1	3	1			1	12					
4	3	1				15	2	2		14		
8	9	3				7	8	1		12		
16	7	4				2	1	3				
32	1	3				1	1					
>32	1											

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin		
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Negative/Absent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available		
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Present	Negative/Absent	Not Available	Not Available		
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	64	128	128	128	2	16	16	64
N of tested isolates	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29
N of resistant isolates	26	29	4	4	6	29	4	4	0	0	0	0
MIC												
64		11			2							
>64		4			1							

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Meat from pig - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Austria

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim		
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2		
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25		
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32		
N of tested isolates	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29		
N of resistant isolates	29	2	29	28	5	6	0	1	0	6	21	13	0	16		
MIC																
<=0.015						19										
<=0.03										28						
0.03						3										
0.064						1										
<=0.25													28	4		
0.25						2										
<=0.5				1					22							
0.5													1	6		
<=1							29									
1				6					6							
<=2		2											12			
2			3	7												
<=4										23						
4		11	3	7									4			
>4			23													
<=8					20						1					
8		11			5	4										
>8				3												
16		3			4					1						
32		1			1									2		
>32														16		
64					2								1			
>64	29	1											12			

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29
N of resistant isolates	29	2	29	28	5	6	0	1	0	6	21	13	0	16
MIC														
128					2					2				
>128										4				
>1024											21			

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Meat from pig - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON pnl2

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Germany

AM substance	Cefepime	Cefotaxim	Cefotaxime + Clavulanic acid	Cefoxitin	Ceftazidim	Ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid	Ertapenem	Imipenem	Meropenem	Temocillin	
Cefotaxime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	
Ceftazidime synergy test	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Positive/Pres ent	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	
ECOFF	0.125	0.25	0.25	8	0.5	0.5	0.064	0.5	0.125	32	
Lowest limit	0.064	0.25	0.064	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.015	0.12	0.03	0.5	
Highest limit	32	64	64	64	128	128	2	16	16	64	
N of tested isolates	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
N of resistant isolates	3	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	
MIC											
<=0.015							2				
<=0.03									3		
0.03							1				
<=0.064			3								
<=0.12						2	2				
0.25						1	1				
1					1						
2					1						
4	1			3	1					3	
16	2	1									
64	2										

Table Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified in Meat from pig - fresh

Sampling Stage: Retail

Sampling Type: food sample - meat

Sampling Context: Monitoring

Sampler: Official sampling

Sampling Strategy: Objective sampling

Programme Code: ESBL MON

Analytical Method:

Country of Origin: Germany

AM substance	Ampicillin	Azithromycin	Cefotaxim	Ceftazidim	Chloramphenicol	Ciprofloxacin	Colistin	Gentamicin	Meropenem	Nalidixic acid	Sulfamethoxazole	Tetracycline	Tigecycline	Trimethoprim
ECOFF	8	16	0.25	0.5	16	0.064	2	2	0.125	16	64	8	1	2
Lowest limit	1	2	0.25	0.5	8	0.015	1	0.5	0.03	4	8	2	0.25	0.25
Highest limit	64	64	4	8	128	8	16	32	16	128	1024	64	8	32
N of tested isolates	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
N of resistant isolates	3	0	3	3	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	3	0	2
MIC														
<=0.015						2								
<=0.03										3				
<=0.25													3	1
<=0.5								2						
<=1							3							
1				1					1					
2				1										
<=4											2			
4			3	1										
>4			3											
<=8					3									
8						1								
16											1			
>32														2
>64	3											3		
>128										1				
>1024												2		

OTHER ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE TABLES

Specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/carbapenemase-producing bacteria and specific monitoring of carbapenemase-producing bacteria, in the absence of isolate detected

Programme Code	Matrix Detailed	Zoonotic Agent Detailed	Sampling Strategy	Sampling Stage	Sampling Details	Sampling Context	Sampler	Sample Type	Sampling Unit Type	Sample Origin	Comment	Total Units Tested	Total Units Positive
CARBA MON	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified	Objective sampling	Slaughterhouse	N_A	Monitoring	Official sampling	animal sample - caecum	slaughter animal batch	Austria	N_A	300	0
												Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified
	Austria	N_A	267	0									
	Brazil	N_A	1	0									
	Germany	N_A	10	0									
	Ireland	N_A	2	0									
	Netherlands	N_A	1	0									
	Romania	N_A	1	0									
	United States	N_A	3	0									
	Unknown	N_A	6	0									
	Uruguay	N_A	2	0									
	Meat from pig - fresh	Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified	Objective sampling	Retail	N_A	Monitoring	Official sampling	food sample - meat	batch (food/feed)	Austria	N_A	258	0
										Germany	N_A	16	0
										Netherlands	N_A	1	0
										Spain	N_A	2	0
										Unknown	N_A	25	0
	Pigs - fattening pigs	Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified	Objective sampling	Slaughterhouse	N_A	Monitoring	Official sampling	animal sample - caecum	slaughter animal batch	Austria	N_A	283	0

Latest Transmission set

Table Name	Last submitted dataset transmission date
Antimicrobial Resistance	20-Nov-2018
Esbl	23-Jul-2018
Animal Population	23-Jul-2018
Disease Status	23-Jul-2018
Food Borne Outbreaks	23-Jul-2018
Prevalence	23-Jul-2018

Austria, Text 2017

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1. Institutions and Laboratories involved in zoonoses monitoring and reporting

Central Veterinary Services of the former Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF), now Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection:

Provided data concerning tuberculosis and brucellosis in animals, trichinellosis and echinococcosis in animals;

Revision of the draft of the Trend Report;

Approval of the Trend Report for Submission.

Food Office of the former Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF), now Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection:

Revision of the draft of the Trend Report

Feed Office of the Federal Ministry of Sustainability and Tourism:

Revision of the draft of the Trend Report

Provincial Veterinary Services, nine provinces, one Veterinary Service per province:

Provided data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals

Local/District health authorities as part of each local administration authority

("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"); one or more official physicians per district:

Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food-borne outbreaks

Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the Business Area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR) of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:

Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporters);

Mapping of food and feed data and food-borne outbreaks;

In-depth description of zoonoses in Austria

creation of xml-files, upload of data to DCF

Statistics Austria is the independent and non-profit-making federal institution that provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies:

Demographic and livestock census data

Department for Infectious Epidemiology, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:

Provides the complete list of food borne outbreaks

National Reference Centre for Salmonella, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:

Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and results of antimicrobial susceptibility testing

National Reference Centre for E. coli including VTEC, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:

Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals

National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:

Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals

National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:
Data concerning tuberculosis in animals

National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:
Data concerning rabies in humans and animals

Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU) of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna:
Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs in all Austrian provinces

Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna, Regional Food Laboratory:
Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs collected in Vienna

Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg, Regional Food Laboratory:
Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs collected in Vorarlberg

Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control, Regional Food Laboratory:
Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs collected in Carinthia

National Reference Laboratory for Listeria, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:
Typing of Listeria monocytogenes isolates from food and humans

Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI), Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:
Provides data concerning monitoring programmes in animals

Officially authorized Veterinarians of the Provincial Veterinary Services:
The officially authorized Veterinarians inter alia do the sampling at slaughterhouses and in poultry farms.

Food inspectors of the provinces:
Food inspectors inter alia do the sampling at retail, catering, restaurants and processing plants

Austrian Poultry Health Data (PHD), Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. Salmonella control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers:
Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz of the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES:
Data concerning feeding stuffs

2. Animal population

1. Sources of information and the date(s) (months, years) the information relates to

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings and stocks: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The numbers of holdings, flocks and animals presented here are part of the Salmonella control program and are based on the Poultry Health Data. In Austria there are also holdings with a small number of animals that are not covered by the Salmonella control program and these numbers of holdings, flocks and animals are not presented in the following table.

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughterings is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughterings (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughterings is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians) plus not-examined slaughterings (out of a pig-random-sample-survey) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughterings is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

2. Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the production types covered

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 163/2012 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

3. Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.48 % of all pigs are kept in 83.25 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 73.08 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 75.45 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 69.18 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 78.18 % of the goats are kept there.

Solipeds: 67.93 % of the soliped holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 71.29% of the solipeds are kept there.

Deer: 89.05% of the deer holdings are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria; 90.03% of the deer are kept there.

Cattle: 71.40% of the cattle holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and Carinthia; 77.75% of the cattle are kept there.

Maps and tables available:

http://www.statistik.at/web_de/statistiken/wirtschaft/land_und_forstwirtschaft/viehbestand_tierische_erzeugung/viehbestand/index.html (Tabellen, Interaktive Karten, Thematische Karten, Stat. Datenbanken etc.)

4. Additional information

Numbers of holdings, flocks and animals and slaughtered animals and changes compared with the previous year are published in the national zoonosis brochure.

3. General evaluation: *Brucella* spp.

1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds (OBF). According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially *B. melitensis* free (ObmF).

2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans

Brucellosis is only found sporadically as a human infectious disease in Austria. In the last years all cases in Austria were confirmed as imported cases or the source of infection could not be determined. The number of brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases. In 2017, six cases have been reported to the EMS, four cases confirmed as imported for the two other cases no information was available.

3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union

No recent actions in Austria; continuation of the existing control programs.

4. Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals, the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Cattle *Brucella abortus*

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Holdings with and without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated. If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out. Abortion or premature birth in context with epidemiological investigation: must be notified to the district veterinarian (§7 and §25 of Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). Tissues from the aborted fetus and blood from the affected cows are sampled immediately post abortion and tested for brucellosis by microbiological and serological methods.

Following specimen are taken and analyzed: bulk milk, blood samples, aborted fetus, diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus

(stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node. After abortion or premature birth: tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

For analysis standard methods are used:

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA Brucella Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwPSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE Brucella abortus Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the I-ELISA single serum samples were tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and two ELISAs for verification. Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (AHVLA, ANSES) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for those Austrian Veterinary Institutes which are involved in brucellosis surveillance and diagnosis. Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforths method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were inoculated. The culture media were incubated for 5 days at 37° C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using Brucella antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of Brucella abortus, Brucella melitensis and Brucella suis. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

An animal is considered to be positive for bovine brucellosis, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a Brucella abortus-infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get sufficient information about the reacting animal.

2. Measures in place

According to the Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Vaccination is not allowed (§6 Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013)

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

Abortion or premature birth; Notification of abortions in context with epidemiological investigations is mandatory: Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013 and Venereal diseases act, Federal Law Gazette no. 22/1949 as amended; The livestock owner has to notify the abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the district veterinarian (Bezirksverwaltungsbehoerde). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehoerde).

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2017, 1,324 bulk milk samples and 10,952 blood samples from 1,295 herds have been tested for Brucella antibodies. No cases have been detected, so the total population of 1,957,196 animals in 60,675 herds keeps the official brucellosis free status. The status officially free has been achieved in 1999 and has been kept since then.

5. Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and in the Annual Veterinary Report.

5. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Sheep and Goats *Brucella melitensis*

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

The entire country is free of *B. melitensis*. According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially *B. melitensis* free (ObmF). To maintain that status according to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. In cases of abortion, aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal were also investigated. The sampling was performed mainly during the cold season, between November and May when the animals have been kept in the stables.

For monitoring, blood samples according to a sampling plan are taken. In suspicion of clinical cases, aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal are examined. Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the approved laboratories.

Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from AHVLA and ANSES. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes. Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforths method. Columbia agar (bioMrieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37° C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or a positive serological test result.

2. Measures in place

According to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

According to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) vaccination is not allowed.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority
Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis is mandatory according to BGBl. 391/1995 (Brucellose-Verordnung).
4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In 2017, 19,503 animals out of 1,591 herds of sheep and goats have been examined for B. melitensis antibodies, No cases have been detected therefor the whole population of 566,464 sheep and goats out of 24,556 herds keeps the status officially Brucella melitensis free. The status officially free has been achieved in 2001 and has been kept since then.
5. Additional information
The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and in the Annual Veterinary Report.

6. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Pigs <i>Brucella suis</i>
1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system
<p>For brucellosis in pigs there is no monitoring program, examinations are performed only targeted, following abortion and in positive cases of contact holdings. According to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008, suspicious clinical cases are investigated by testing abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal or tissues.</p> <p>Samples are tested using Brucella ELISA and CFT. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (AHVLA and ANSES) with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes. Bacteriology: - Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforths method.- Columbia agar (bioMrieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using Brucella antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of Brucella abortus, Brucella melitensis and Brucella suis. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).</p> <p>An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (B. abortus used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of B. suis.</p>
2. Measures in place
In case of positive findings, no mandatory measures are foreseen only notification is required. Vaccination is not performed.
3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.
4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In 2017, one outbreak and nine contact holdings have been detected.
5. Additional information
The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and in the Annual Veterinary Report.

7. General evaluation: <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.
1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country
In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of cases of human campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis has been widening. In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 7,084 cases in 2016. The number of <i>Campylobacter</i> cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS.
2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans
In 2017, a new peak in the number of human cases has been reached, 7,201 laboratory confirmed cases have been notified to EMS. The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cows raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.
3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union
The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of <i>Campylobacter</i> -prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of <i>Campylobacter</i> in broilers and turkey was performed according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out in 2014. In 2017 no specific program was foreseen in animals. Austrian provinces published guidance on the procedure and joint actions in cases of food-borne diseases. As an example the guidance "Personal control measures in the case of food-borne diseases" part 1, salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis is available (in German language): https://www.wien.gv.at/gesundheit/sandirektion/pdf/leitlinie-bei-lebensmittelbedingten-erkrankungen.pdf .
4. Additional information
If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or

animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.
The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

8. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Campylobacter* in foodstuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling scheme:

In 2017, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2017 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Probenplan und Berichtsschema 2017“ (BMGF-75500/0158-II/B/13/2016) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly, depending on their risk categorization. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). Sampling by the competent authority is distributed evenly throughout the year for scheduled samples, which focused on fresh meat and meat preparations from poultry. In 2017, the sampling plan intended approximately 23,500 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2017, two food campaigns are dealing with *Campylobacter* and reported to EFSA in Chapter “Additional information”.

Testing scheme:

Campylobacter is detected according to ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006. *Campylobacter* isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. There *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* from the sample independent of the microbiological method (quantitative or qualitative) used is defined as a positive finding. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) and whole genome sequencing (WGS) are available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

2. Measures in place

No measures in place.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

No notification system in place.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of

infection^(e)

In total 602 food samples have been tested for Campylobacter (237 Campylobacter positives). Fresh meat from broilers has been tested at different sampling stages. At processing plants 22 samples have been tested for Campylobacter, with 15 positive results (14 *C. jejuni*, 1 *C. coli*). At the sampling stage retail 42 (32 *C. jejuni*, 8 *C. coli*, 2 Campylobacter unspecified) out of 65 samples have been positive for Campylobacter (64.6%, CI: 52-75%) in fresh broiler meat.

Fresh meat from turkey (at retail and catering) had a positivity rate of 37.8% (CI: 31-46%; 59 positive samples out of 156).

In total, 163 meat preparations from broiler, turkey and unspecified poultry meat (intended to be eaten cooked) have been tested with a prevalence of 38.7% (CI: 32-46%).

In 45 raw milk samples from cow, sheep and goat no Campylobacter was detected. In 2 other products of animal origin Campylobacter was detected, whereas in 54 other food samples of diverse food categories (meat, meat products, salad, fruits) no Campylobacter was found.

Since 2013 the percentage of Campylobacter positive broiler meat samples at retail has been balanced around 65% (2017) with a minimum of 58% (2014) and maximum 69% (2016). At processing/slaughterhouse stage the range of positivity rate is higher in the last five years (56%-89%), including huge fluctuations without recognizing any trend. Turkey meat might show a trend, as in 2013 the percentage of Campylobacter positive samples increased steadily from 22% (2013) to 38% (2017), without huge fluctuations.

No source attribution modelling has been performed in/for Austria.

5. Additional information**Campaign A_049_17:**

Campylobacter in food – meat from duck, meat from geese - fresh– single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: October to November

Type of specimen taken: Fresh duck meat, fresh geese meat;

Results of the investigation: 46 samples were tested for Campylobacter, 31 positive for Campylobacter

Additional information: Samples were also tested for Salmonella

Campaign A_801_17:

Campylobacter in food –turkey meat- fresh– single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: June to July

Type of specimen taken: fresh turkey meat, no meat preparations; 17 samples from organic production and 92 samples conventionally raised turkey.

Results of the investigation: 109 samples were tested for Campylobacter, 45 were positive for Campylobacter

Additional information: Samples were also tested for Salmonella

9. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Animals and *Campylobacter* spp.

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

In 2017, no program to control Campylobacter in animals was foreseen.

10. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system:
Cronobacter sakazakii in foodstuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling scheme:

In 2017, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2017 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Probenplan und Berichtsschema 2017“ (BMGF-75500/0158-II/B/13/2016) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly, depending on their risk categorization. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). Sampling by the competent authority is distributed evenly throughout the year for scheduled samples, infant formula is focussed on. In 2017, the sampling plan intended approximately 23,500 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others for zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2017, one food campaign is dealing with *Cronobacter sakazakii* and reported to EFSA in chapter “Additional information”.

Testing scheme: *Cronobacter sakazakii* is analysed according to ISO 22964:2017

2. Measures in place

Not available

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

Not available

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

See table

5. Additional information

Campaign A_011_17:

Cronobacter sakazakii in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: March to April

Type of specimen taken: Infant formula

Results of the investigation: 38 samples were tested for *Cronobacter sakazakii*: none positive
Additional information: Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*: none positive

11. General evaluation: *Echinococcus* spp.

1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

From 2013 to 2016, the Institute for Veterinary Disease Control Innsbruck of the AGES performed investigations about the prevalence of *E. multilocularis* in foxes in the two Austrian provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg. The examinations showed that 33% of foxes in Tyrol (145 out of 434 foxes tested) and 45% in Vorarlberg (183 out of 405 foxes tested) were infested with *E. multilocularis* (Glawischnig W und Walser F, 2017. Abschlussberichte: Untersuchungen zum aktuellen Vorkommen des Fünfgliedrigen Fuchsbandwurmes bei Füchsen in Tirol und in Vorarlberg).

In 2017, 40 cases of cystic and ten cases of alveolar echinococcosis were detected in humans. The higher number of findings seems to be an artefact due to a higher number of samples sent for confirmation to the respective National Reference Centre.

Relevance of the findings in animals: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-45 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

4. Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

12. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Animals and *Echinococcus* spp.

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

In Austria, all slaughtered animals are examined for cysts in the course of the post-mortem meat inspection according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended. Carcasses with very low number of detected cysts are made fit for consumption by deep-freezing overseen by the official veterinarian; if higher numbers of cysts are found the carcasses are declared unfit for human consumption. The cysts are not further specified.

2. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

Concerning the findings of cysts of echinococcosis (cystic or alveolar), no data are available in slaughtered animals.

13. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Histamine in foodstuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling scheme:

In 2017, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2017 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Probenplan und Berichtsschema 2017“ (BMGF-75500/0158-II/B/13/2016) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly, depending on their risk categorization. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). Sampling by the competent authority is distributed evenly throughout the year for scheduled samples, fish, fishery products, and cheese is focussed on. In 2017, the sampling plan intended approximately 23,500 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others for zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2017, two food campaigns are dealing with Histamine and reported to EFSA in chapter “Additional information”.

Testing scheme: Histamine is analysed according to ISO 19343:2017

Definition of units in non-conformity:

>200 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme maturated

>400 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in

brine >400 mg histamine per kg cheese
2. Measures in place
Not available
3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority
Not available
4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In total 218 food samples were tested for histamine (total units in non-conformity: 12). Details can be found in the table.
5. Additional information
<p>Campaign A_030_17: Histamine in food – Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – single (food/feed) – at Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: July to August Type of specimen taken: Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – samples of tuna in open boxes Results of the investigation: 73 samples were tested for histamine: total units in non-conformity: 2 (>200 to <=400 mg/kg), 2 (>400 mg/kg) Additional information: 71 samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.: none positive</p> <p>Campaign A_022_17: Histamine in food – Fish raw – single (food/feed) – at Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: May to June Type of specimen taken: Raw tuna samples at restaurants Results of the investigation: 37 samples were tested for histamine: total units in non-conformity: 2 (>200 to <=400 mg/kg) Additional information: Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.: none positive Samples were also tested for Listeria monocytogenes: none positive</p>

14. General evaluation: *Listeria monocytogenes*

1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). In 2013, 36 cases in 2014, 49 cases were notified in the EMS, 47 in the NRC-L. In 2015, a slight decrease of cases was observed, 38 cases (EMS) or 37 cases (NRLC). In 2016, 46 cases were notified to the EMS. The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2 to 0.9). In 2016, lethality was reported in 7 out of 46 cases in EMS (15 % of cases). Due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. According to the NRC-L, isolates from 44 cases were typed (2 cases were confirmed by PCR, the 28-day lethality was 17 % (8 cases), none of the cases was pregnancy related.

The high fatality rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans

In 2017, 32 cases of laboratory confirmed listeriosis have been notified to the EMS, one case was associated with pregnancy. The 28-day mortality rate was 19% (6 out of 32). In November 2017, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) reported an ongoing multinational listeriosis outbreak with *L. monocytogenes* PCR serovar IVb, multilocus sequence type (MLST) ST6. This outbreak included 26 cases from five European countries, involving in Austria two cases, but both occurred in 2016: one 91-year-old male from Upper Austria and a patient from Salzburg (fatal outcome). See also the chapter "food-borne outbreaks".

Additionally in 2017 two patients with Clonal Type 1234 were registered: an 81-year-old female from Upper Austria and a 29-year-old female from Lower Austria. In January 2018, the Austrian Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Consumer Protection (BMASGK) commissioned the AGES to investigate this cross-border listeriosis outbreak by Clonal Type 1234, which affected seven persons (including one death) in three Austrian provinces between 2015 and 2017. See also the chapter "food-borne outbreaks".

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although raw milk, soft and semi-soft cheeses, ready-to-eat meat products, and smoked salmons are likely candidates as vehicles for infections. The source of an infection often remains unclear.

3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union

In 2017, AGES published guidelines - in close collaboration with the Robert Koch Institute, Berlin - that for the first time gave physicians concrete instructions for dealing with persons who had consumed food that was officially recalled due to *Listeria* contamination: "Product recalls because of *Listeria*: consequences for the doctor consulted?" (Huhulescu S, Allerberger F. (2018) Produktrückrufe wegen Listerien: Konsequenzen für den hinzugezogenen Arzt? *internistische praxis* 58, 737-740)

4. Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send those strains to the respective national reference lab for

typing and comparative analysis.

15. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling scheme:

In 2017, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2017 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Probenplan und Berichtsschema 2017“ (BMGF-75500/0158-II/B/13/2016) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly, depending on their risk categorization. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). Sampling by the competent authority was distributed evenly throughout the year for scheduled samples, with a focus on pasteurized and raw cows’ milk, cheeses, pig meat products, bovine meat products, fishery products, and smoked fish. In 2017, the sampling plan intended approximately 23,500 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others for zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2017, four food campaigns are dealing with *Listeria monocytogenes* and reported to EFSA in chapter “Additional information”.

Testing scheme:

Bacteriological method ISO 11290-1:2017 and ISO 11290-2:2017. For further investigations all isolates from foodstuffs are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria* NRL-L) in Graz. This includes the isolates from process hygiene controls at the production plant, self-monitoring as well as all isolates from regularly testing at retail.

2. Measures in place

The control program/strategies in place:

All isolates from foodstuffs and process hygiene controls from any laboratories within Austria are gathered and typed at the NRL-L. In a first step the species *Listeria monocytogenes* is confirmed by different selective media (e. g. Palcam agar, Ottoviani Agosti agar, Rapid L. mono agar) and/or API, matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI TOF) is available. A serogroup-specific PCR according to Doumith et al. is performed routinely (Doumith et.al. Differentiation of the major *Listeria monocytogenes* serovars by multiplex PCR. J Clin Microbiol (2004); 51, 3819-22). Finally, typing is realized with PFGE to answer type specific questions. In the case of an outbreak the data of the outbreak strain are compared with the existing data base.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken:

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Infections during pregnancy transmitted via food. This folder is available in German, Turkish and Serbo-Croatian (<https://www.ages.at/en/topics/pathogenic-organism/listeria/>) and was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis. Folders of hygiene guidelines on the webpage of the Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection: (<https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/lebensmittel/buch/hygieneleitlinien/hytenell.html>).

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

No notification system in place

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection^(e)

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/17) as in the last 8 years from 2010 onwards. Also none of the 37 samples of raw cows' milk was found positive. In total 824 cheeses were tested and L. monocytogenes could be detected in 3 samples (in one sample also detected by quantitative method <100 cfu/g). In 3 of 7 samples from pig meat products – raw and intended to be eaten raw and in 1 out of 5 samples in fermented sausages from pig meat products L. monocytogenes was qualitatively found. 4 out of 142 samples (2.8 %) of red meat products were found positive in the detection method. And in fermented sausages from red meat 10 out of 94 (10.6 %) were found positive, in one sample detected also by quantitative method <100 cfu/g; all nine the other samples contained Listeria below detection limit of the quantitative method. None of all 53 samples from fishery products revealed a contamination with L. monocytogenes, 1 out of 58 raw fish samples (1.7 %) and none of the 29 smoked fish samples was found positive for L. monocytogenes. Other processed food products and prepared dishes added up to 929 samples of which 10 samples (1.1 %) were found positive (one sample in the quantitative method >100 cfu/g).

5. Additional information

Campaign A_011_17:

Listeria monocytogenes in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: March to April

Type of specimen taken: Infant formula

Results of the investigation: 73 samples were tested for L. monocytogenes: none positive

Additional information: 38 of these samples were also tested for Cronobacter sakazakii: none positive

Campaign A_022_17:

Listeria monocytogenes in food – Fish raw – single (food/feed) – at Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: May to June

Type of specimen taken: Raw tuna samples at restaurants

Results of the investigation: 37 samples were tested for L. monocytogenes: none positive

Additional information: Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.: none positive

Samples were also tested for Histamine: total units in non-conformity: 2 (>200 to <=400 mg/kg)

Campaign A_802_17:

L. monocytogenes in food – cheeses made from cows' and sheep milk – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: July to August

Type of specimen taken: Cheeses made from cows' and sheep milk, sliced and packed directly at retail

outlets

Results of the investigation: 136 samples were tested for *L. monocytogenes*: none positive

Additional information: None

Campaign A_600_17:

The aim of campaign A_600 is to control the implementation of the general and specific hygiene requirements as well as the verification of self-monitoring checks according Reg. 2073/2005. Since 2014, all Austrian high-risk producers of milk, fish and meat were considered in this campaign, except for companies processing less than 500 tons of milk or less than 150 tons of meat per year. This is the first time reporting food monitoring data to EFSA according Reg 2073/2005.

The official food control conducts the inspections, which are very detailed with particular attention to self-checks, including a food specific questionnaire. Product and environmental sampling are part of the inspections. Only results from product sampling are included in this report. An elaborate description of the campaign, including results from 2014 and 2015 is published : Stadlmueller, Lisa, Monika Matt, Hans Peter Stueger, Tanja Komericki-Strimitzer, Karen Jebousek, Martin Luttenfeldner, and Klemens Fuchs. "An Operational Hygiene Inspection Scoring System for Austrian High-Risk Companies Producing Food of Animal Origin." *Food Control* 77 (July 2017): 121–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2017.01.019>.

L. monocytogenes in food – meat, mixed meat - meat preparation; meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products; dairy products (excluding cheeses) – butter; fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat, cheeses; other processed food products and prepared dishes – at processing plant – surveillance, based on Regulation 2073/2005 – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: January 2017 - January 2018

Type of specimen taken: various, different types of food of animal origin; typically produced products have been sampled during inspections according to regulation 2073.

Results of the investigation: In total 1.683 samples from the environment (1.392) and food (291) have been collected. VTEC was tested in 12 cheese and sausages samples (all negative), *Salmonella* was tested in 17 samples of all categories (all negative), and *Listeria monocytogenes* was tested in 265 samples resulting in 12 *Listeria* spp. positive (e.g. *Listeria welshimeri*, *Listeria innocua*), and 4 *Listeria monocytogenes* positives (sliced "Karreespeck", two different types of Bratwurst; typical piece of meat for barbeque ("Schopf")).

16. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: animals and *Listeria*

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Due to the low significance there is no monitoring foreseen in animals.

17. General evaluation: Rabies

1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s. In 2013 due to official rabies free status in Austria (since 28.9.2008) oral vaccination of foxes has been suspended; monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union" (<http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/doc/67e.pdf>).

2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans

In 2017, no case of rabies was detected in humans or animals in Austria.

3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union

Not of relevance yet.

4. Additional information

Not of relevance

18. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: All animals, Rabies virus

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Wild animals: According to the decree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012) monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union. Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes only brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (approx. 0,5 cm³ of brain stem and hippocampus) is examined.

Other animals: Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

The routine test is the fluorescent antibody test (FAT). In case of animals after biting a person and in any inconclusive FAT-cases RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) and RT-PCR are performed. MIT (mouse inoculation test) is only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation. An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the RT-PCR or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

2. Measures in place

Wild animals: Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten; degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012).
Other animals: According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42.
Due to official status rabies free no vaccination of foxes is performed. Voluntary vaccination of pets.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases found in animals in 2017.

5. Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies. In 2013, oral vaccination of foxes was suspended all over Austria.

19. General evaluation: *Salmonella* spp.

1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. In 2016, the number of laboratory confirmed notified salmonellosis cases (table 2, n = 1,415 cases) decreased compared to 2015 by 6.5% and reached the lowest level since notification has been made mandatory. Human campylobacteriosis is the most commonly reported food-borne zoonoses in Austria although salmonellosis remains relevant to human health.

2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans

In 2017, 1,672 laboratory confirmed, food-borne cases of salmonellosis have been notified to EMS. The slight increase of cases compared to 2016 was due to an increase of cases by serovar *S. Enteritidis*, in the first line of phage type 8 (doubled cases compared to 2016). The *Salmonella*-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30 % in 1999 to less than 5.5 % in 2009, since 2012 it has increased from 9.3 % to 10 % in 2013, 11.5 % in 2014, 14% in 2015, and to 15% in 2016 due to the fact that *S. Infantis*-prevalence is still high in poultry meat (12%). The consumption of *Salmonella*-contaminated eggs and egg products is presumably the main cause for human infections with *S. Enteritidis* even though *S. Enteritidis* was detected only in 15 out of 2,880 flocks of laying hens (0.5%) within the National Control Program.

In 2017, Austria achieved the EU-targets for *Salmonella* serovars in populations of laying hens, broilers, and turkeys but just missed those for breeding hens. The results show that the measures taken like the vaccination programs and the rigorous hygiene control programs as well as their efficient control must be maintained and must not be softened.

3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of *Salmonella* in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Austrian provinces published guidance on the procedure and joint actions in cases of food-borne diseases. As an example the guidance "Personal control measures in the case of food-borne diseases" part 1, salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis is available (only in German language):

<https://www.wien.gv.at/gesundheit/sandirektion/pdf/leitlinie-bei-lebensmittelbedingten-erkrankungen.pdf> .

4. Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

20. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system:
Salmonella in foodstuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling scheme:

In 2017, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2017 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Probenplan und Berichtsschema 2017“ (BMGF-75500/0158-II/B/13/2016) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly, depending on their risk categorization. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). Sampling by the competent authority was distributed evenly throughout the year for scheduled samples, with a focus on food of animal origin (meat, eggs), but almost every food category is tested for *Salmonella*. In 2017, the sampling plan intended approximately 23,500 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2017, four food campaigns are dealing with *Salmonella* and reported to EFSA in Chapter “Additional information”.

Testing scheme:

Bacteriological method ISO 6579:2017. The amount of tested food in general is 25 g. Some exceptions exist, according to the Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005. All *Salmonella* isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* NRC-S) in Graz where those are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally all isolates are tested for their antibiotic susceptibility using the disk diffusion method applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints. In case of an outbreak situation the stored isolates may be further investigated with pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) or multiple-locus variable-number of tandem-repeats analysis (MLVA).

2. Measures in place

No measures in place.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

No notification system in place.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In total 4,728 food samples have been tested for *Salmonella* comprising 74 isolates and 73 positive samples in 2017.

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh broiler meat samples in 15.1% (16 out of 106) and in 5.8% of fresh turkey meat samples (11 out of 190). In 13 of the remaining fresh meat samples (n = 73) from duck meat, geese meat and unspecified poultry meat *Salmonella* has been detected. Meat preparations, raw but intended to be eaten cooked contained *Salmonella* in 16.4% of broiler meat, whereas 19 of 125 poultry meat preparations (unspecified) were tested positive (15.2%).

None of the poultry meat products, no matter if cooked or raw, contained any Salmonella (42 samples tested). Segregating the data for processing plants and slaughter houses (fresh broiler meat), 4 samples were tested positive for Salmonella (29 samples tested, 13.8%, CI: 8-29%). At processing plants the four Salmonella serovars found were three times S. Infantis. At the stage of slaughter, no Salmonella has been detected.

45 Salmonella serovars have been detected in poultry meat. The most prevalent serovar detected in poultry and products thereof is S. Infantis (51% of all serovars), as in the previous years.

In total 832 samples of meat, minced meat, meat products and meat preparations (poultry not included) were tested, with 10 samples positive for Salmonella.

No Salmonella were found in 987 samples of milk, dairy products and cheeses, as in the years 2008-2016.

2,171 samples of different matrices were tested for Salmonella, resulting in two positive ones.

All egg products (liquid, dried), were negative for Salmonella (142 tested samples). Out of the 138 samples from packing centres, processing plants, retail, catering or wholesale no sample was tested positive for Salmonella in table eggs in 2017, as in previous years.

Since 2013 the percentage of Salmonella positive broiler meat samples at retail is balanced around 15% (2017) with a minimum of 10% (2013) and maximum 23% (peak in 2015). Since 2012 an increasing trend for S. Infantis is observed in fresh broiler meat at retail in Austria (2012: 4,4% of fresh broiler meat samples contain S. Infantis, in 2016: 21%). In 2017 all Salmonella isolates from fresh broiler meat are S. Infantis, though the positivity rate decreased.

At processing/slaughterhouse stage a peak with 18% in 2015 is decreasing to a positivity rate of 14% in 2017 Turkey meat might show a trend, as since 2014 the percentage of Salmonella positive samples increased steadily from 3.3% (2014) to 5.8% (2017), without huge fluctuations – in 2013 the positivity rate was the highest. As Salmonella is rarely detected in eggs and egg products no trends are observable for these food categories.

No source attribution modelling has been performed in/for Austria.

5. Additional information

Campaign A_022_17:

Salmonella in food – Fish raw – single (food/feed) – at Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: May to June

Type of specimen taken: Raw tuna samples at restaurants

Results of the investigation: 37 samples were tested for Salmonella spp.: none positive

Additional information: Samples were also tested for Listeria monocytogenes: none positive

Samples were also tested for histamine: total units in non-conformity: 2 (>200 to <=400 mg/kg)

Campaign A_030_17:

Salmonella spp. in food – Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – single (food/feed) – at Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: July to August

Type of specimen taken: Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – samples of tuna in open boxes

Results of the investigation: 71 samples were tested for Salmonella: none positive

Additional information: Samples were also tested for histamine: total units in non-conformity: 2 (>200 to <=400 mg/kg), 2 (>400 mg/kg)

Campaign A_049_17:

Salmonella spp. in food – meat from duck, meat from geese - fresh– single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: October to November

Type of specimen taken: Fresh duck meat, fresh geese meat;

Results of the investigation: 46 samples were tested for Salmonella, 6 positive for Salmonella (3x S. Newport in meat of geese, S. Typhimurium in one sample of meat from duck and one from goose meat, 1x S. Serogroup C in meat from duck meat)

Additional information: Samples were also tested for Campylobacter

Campaign A_801_17:

Salmonella spp. in food – Meat from turkey – fresh – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Frequency of the sampling: Investigation period: June to July

Type of specimen taken: fresh turkey meat, no meat preparations; 21 samples from organic production and 12 samples conventionally raised turkey.

Results of the investigation: 133 samples were tested for Campylobacter, 6 positive for Salmonella

Additional information: 109 of these samples were also tested for Campylobacter

21. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Salmonella* spp. in breeding flocks of *Gallus gallus*

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

There are only parent flocks in Austria, no elite or grandparent flocks.

Sampling strategy

The permanent monitoring plan performed by the national programme takes place at hatcheries and at farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities. If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm (5 pairs of boot swabs/5 samples of pooled faeces made up of separate samples – 200 to 300g each- and 2 dust samples). If a parent flock tests positive for other *Salmonella* serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimize biosecurity if needed.

Frequency of sampling

Every flock is tested at day one (day-old chicks). During rearing every flock is tested at the age of 4 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit (= routine testing). If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results a follow-up confirmation test can be performed in exceptional cases (this is decided by the official veterinarian in charge).

During the production period, monitoring is performed according to CR (EU) No 200/2010 and the national programme. It takes place at the hatchery and/or on the farm; at the hatchery, each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm, each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer (additionally at least every twelve weeks the sampling has to be done by the private veterinarian) and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within 8 weeks before slaughter).

Type of specimen taken

From day-old chicks visibly soiled hatcher basket liners or dead chicks (if available) are sampled. During rearing boot swabs or pooled faeces are taken (routine testing). For confirmation testing, 5 pairs of boot swabs/5 samples of pooled faeces (which are made up of separate samples – 200 to 300g each) and 2 dust samples have to be taken. During the production period, on the farm boot swabs or pooled faeces are taken; in the hatchery, dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs are sampled (routine testing). For confirmation testing, 5 pairs of boot swabs/5 samples of pooled faeces (which are made up of separate samples – 200 to 300g each) and 2 dust samples are taken.

A positive case is defined if *Salmonella* spp. has been isolated from samples taken.

The diagnosis is performed according to ISO 6579-1:2017. All isolates obtained in the primary laboratories must be sent to the NRC *Salmonella*, where they are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

The link to the programme approved by the EC is:

https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/cff_animal_vet-progs_2017-8_dec-2016-2444-

ec_salmonella_breeding_gal_aut.pdf
2. Measures in place
<p>Vaccination policy: The national programme for parent flocks includes mandatory vaccination against <i>S. Enteritidis</i> for all breeding flocks.</p> <p>As other preventive measures the level of biosecurity was increased.</p> <p>The Austrian control programme is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2010.</p> <p>In case of positive findings (confirmed) measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation are performed: banning of the incriminated sector of the holding; elimination (culling or slaughtering) of the infected flock; disposal of the hatched eggs; abolishing of the restriction after cleaning, disinfection and disinfection control; if necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection.</p> <p>The link to the programme approved by the EC is: https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/cff_animal_vet-progs_2017-8_dec-2016-2444-ec_salmonella_breeding_gal_aut.pdf</p>
3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority
<p>Yes, notification is mandatory. All positive findings in breeding flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the Department in charge within the Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection.</p>
4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infectio
<p>In 2017, the target was not met because target serovars were detected in two out of 157 breeding flocks (1.3%), both times S. Infantis was found. The two positive flocks were both flocks for the broiler production line.</p> <p>In the last five years (since 2013) the target was always achieved, with only one flock positive for target serovars, one in 2013 (S. Enteritidis) and one in 2015 (S. Typhimurium).</p>
5. Additional information
<p>The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonosis brochure (available on www.ages.at; last available report: https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/005360ddb1c32a46ebd596da3c431f4918224ddb/fileadmin/AGES_2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Zoonosen/Zoonosenbrochure-2016_EN_1h_BF.PDF), the report "Ergebnisse des <i>Salmonella</i>-Bekämpfungsprogrammes" (https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/6befb10c8a451e40b61775770e746636e6b3967f/fileadmin/AGES_2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Salmonellen/Bericht_Salmonellabekprog_2016_final.pdf)</p>

22. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Salmonella* spp. in laying hens

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling strategy

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks by the private veterinarian; two pairs of boot swabs are taken. At least one testing per year is done by an official veterinarian (boot swabs, dust samples and faeces for residue testing are taken) according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011. Finally, at the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Frequency of sampling

Chicks are tested at day one (day-old chicks). During rearing, animals are tested 2 more times: week 8 to 12 and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit. During production, each flock is tested every 15 weeks; an official veterinarian samples every flock at least once a year according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011. At the end of the laying phase, at the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, last sampling of the flock is performed (according to CR (EU) Nr. 200/2012).

As part of the self-inspection, environmental samples are taken at the egg packing centres and tested for *Salmonella*.

Types of specimen taken

On day one, visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available are sampled. During the rearing period, boot swabs or pooled faeces samples are taken. During production, two pairs of boot swabs or pooled faeces (in holdings with enriched cages) are taken when sampled by the food business operator (samples are taken by a private veterinarian). Official controls are performed taking additional 100 grams of dust /dust swabs of at least 900 cm² surface area in total and 150g of pooled faeces from 60 places for antimicrobial residues testing.

As part of the self-inspection, environmental samples are taken at the egg packing centres and tested for *Salmonella*.

A positive case is defined if *Salmonella* spp. has been isolated from samples taken or tests for antimicrobials are positive.

The diagnosis is performed according to ISO 6579-1:2017. All isolates obtained in the primary laboratories must be sent to the NRC *Salmonella*, where they are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. If of a flock is suspected as the source of a food-borne outbreak, the isolate is further typed using molecular biology techniques (PFGE, VNTR, WGS).

The link to the programme approved by the EC is:

https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/cff_animal_vet-progs_2017-8_dec-2016-2444-ec_salmonella_laying_gg_aut.pdf

2. Measures in place

Vaccination policy: The national programme for layers includes mandatory vaccination against *S. Enteritidis* for all laying flocks. Flocks are vaccinated during rearing phase.

As other preventive measures the level of biosecurity was increased.

Eggs from *Salmonella* positive flocks are not allowed to be sold as class A eggs, only after heat treatment (pasteurized eggs); if a flock is confirmed as the source of a food-borne outbreak, culling if the flock is foreseen. EU Regulation No 1237/2007 is in force.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

Yes, notification is mandatory. All positive findings in laying flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the department in charge within the Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2017, the target was met. In 2017, 2,088 laying hen flocks were in production, in 33 (1.1%) flocks *Salmonella* spp. were detected, target serovars were found in 16 (0.6%) flocks, 15-times *S. Enteritidis* and one time *S. Typhimurium*.

Since the implementation of the Salmonella control programme, Austria has met the targets with the only exception of 2009. Since then, the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. decreased to a minimum of 0.9% in 2015; in 2016, 1.6% of the layer flocks were found to be positive with *Salmonella* spp..

5. Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonosis brochure (available on www.ages.at; last available report:

https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/005360ddb1c32a46ebd596da3c431f4918224ddb/fileadmin/AGES2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Zoonosen/Zoonosenbroschuere-2016_EN_1h_BF.PDF), the report "Ergebnisse des *Salmonella*-Bekämpfungsprogrammes" (https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/6befb10c8a451e40b61775770e746636e6b3967f/fileadmin/AGES2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Salmonellen/Bericht_Salmonellabekprog_2016_final.pdf)

23. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Salmonella* spp. in broilers

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling strategy

Within 3 weeks before the birds are moved to the slaughterhouse, 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken on the farm. 10 % of all flocks produced per year have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EC) No 200/2012 is in force since 01.01.2009. Other programs are not intended; At slaughter house, samples are taken according to Commission Regulation 2073/2005.

A positive case is defined if *Salmonella* spp. has been isolated from samples taken.

The diagnosis is performed according to ISO 6579-1:2017. All isolates obtained in the primary laboratories must be sent to the NRC *Salmonella*, where they are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. If of a flock is suspected as the source of a food-borne outbreak, the isolate is further typed using molecular biology techniques (PFGE, VNTR, WGS).

The link to the programme approved by the EC is:

https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/cff_animal_vet-progs_2017-8_dec-2016-2444-ec_salmonella_broiler_gal_aut.pdf

2. Measures in place

Salmonella - vaccination of broiler flocks is not performed in Austria. The level of biosecurity has been increased. The Austrian control programme is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

Yes, notification is mandatory. All positive findings in broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the department in charge within the Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection. Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2017, the target was met. In 2017, 5,088 broiler flocks, including 128 flocks of brothers of laying hens were produced. For the first time in addition to broilers, brothers of laying hens were raised. *Salmonella* spp. was detected in 183 (3.6%) flocks, *S. Infantis* in 117 flocks. Target serovars were identified in three flocks (*S. Enteritidis*).

With exception of the first year of the control program (2009), the target was always achieved. The *Salmonella* spp. prevalence was lowest in 2011 (2.4%) and reached its maximum in 2016 with 3.8% positive flocks.

5. Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonosis brochure (available on www.ages.at; last

available report:

https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/005360ddb1c32a46ebd596da3c431f4918224ddb/fileadmin/AGES2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Zoonosen/Zoonosenbroschuere-2016_EN_1h_BF.PDF),

the report "Ergebnisse des *Salmonella*-Bekämpfungsprogrammes"

(https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/6befb10c8a451e40b61775770e746636e6b3967f/fileadmin/AGES2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Salmonellen/Bericht_Salmonellabekprog_2016_final.pdf)

24. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Salmonella* spp. In turkeys

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

There are no turkey breeding flocks in Austria.

Sampling strategy

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken on the farm. 10 % of all flocks produced per year have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012 is in force. There are no other programs established.

Sampling frequency

Within 3 weeks before the birds are moved to the slaughterhouse, 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken at the farm.

Types of specimen taken

If the flock is sampled by the food business operator, two pairs of boot swabs per flock are taken by the private veterinarian. During official sampling, two pairs of boot swabs per flock and 60 pooled faeces samples (150g) are collected. At slaughter house samples according to Commission Regulation 2073/2005 are taken.

A positive case is defined if *Salmonella* spp. has been isolated from samples taken.

The diagnosis is performed according to ISO 6579-1:2017. All isolates obtained in the primary laboratories must be sent to the NRC *Salmonella*, where they are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. If of a flock is suspected as the source of a food-borne outbreak, the isolate is further typed using molecular biology techniques (PFGE, VNTR, WGS).

The link to the programme approved by the EC is:

https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/cff_animal_vet-progs_2017-8_dec-2016-2444-ec_salmonella_fattening_turkeys_aut.pdf

2. Measures in place

Salmonella - vaccination of turkey flocks is not performed in Austria. The level of biosecurity has been increased. The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

All positive findings in broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the department in charge within the Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2017, the target for turkey fattening flocks was achieved. A total of 444 turkey flocks were produced, *Salmonella* spp. detected in 12 (2.7%) flocks, no target serovars were identified.

Since the implementation of the *Salmonella* control programme, Austria has met the targets. In the years before 2013 the prevalence of *Salmonella* was high in turkey flocks (6-10%), but since 2014 a decrease could be observed, between 3.8% and 2.5%.

5. Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonosis brochure (available on www.ages.at; last

available report:

https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/005360ddb1c32a46ebd596da3c431f4918224ddb/fileadmin/AGES_2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Zoonosen/Zoonosenbroschuere-2016_EN_1h_BF.PDF),

the report "Ergebnisse des *Salmonella*-Bekämpfungsprogrammes"

https://www.ages.at/download/0/0/6befb10c8a451e40b61775770e746636e6b3967f/fileadmin/AGES_2015/Themen/Krankheitserreger_Dateien/Salmonellen/Bericht_Salmonellabekprog_2016_final.pdf)

25. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: *Salmonella* spp. in feeding stuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling strategy: Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling according to an assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Type of specimen taken: Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin, fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets, Oil seed meals and cakes; compound feedingstuffs: feed for farm animals (mainly poultry) and pets.

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

A positive finding is defined as the isolation of *Salmonella* spp. from a sample.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used: Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2017; sample weight: 25 g (samples related to suspected lots or cases are analysed by testing several subsamples in parallel); all isolates are sent to the NRC *Salmonella* are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts. Further thoroughly investigations on feed related contaminations in connection with traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed as well as more frequently processing and pelletizing feed/contaminated feed have contributed to a better feed quality. So during this period a considerable increase of feed hygiene and feed safety could be reached. Additionally a long-term improvement of the *Salmonella*-status of feed, however, can be achieved only by a proactive approach of this issue involving all parties concerned, such as crushing plants, wholesalers and retailers, trader, but also by cooperation and rapid notification of positive findings from poultry farms, food and feed business operators to the competent authority for feed control.

2. Measures in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999, as last amended by BGBl. Nr. 87/2005 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999) and BGBl. Nr. 316/2010 (Futtermittelverordnung 2010) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 100/2007 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007). EC: Reg. (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and Reg. (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to *Salmonella* monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program.

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In five out of 253 samples of feeding stuffs for livestock tested (2,0%) Salmonella have been detected, once each S. Bredeney, S. Cerro, S. Lexington, S. Mbandaka and S. Senftenberg. Additionally, 67 samples of pet food and chewing toys were officially tested in the reporting year, six samples (9%) were Salmonella positive, in one sample three different serovars and in another sample two different serovars were identified. S. Derby und S. Infantis were found in three samples each and once each S. Coeln, S. Livingstone und S. London.
5. Additional information
The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

26. General evaluation: <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>
1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country
Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.
2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans
Toxoplasmosis is a relevant zoonotic disease, because infection only occurs via orally ingestion of oocysts after contact with cats and food contaminated with cat faeces or via consumption of cysts-containing undercooked or raw meat.

27. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Animals and <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>
1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system
Animal samples from livestock and cats are only sent to the laboratory to be tested for Toxoplasma upon clinical suspicion, such as following still births or out of private interest.
2. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In 2017, antibodies to Toxoplasma were found in 12 out of 22 samples from sheep, in 17 out of 26 samples from goat's but not in samples from 28 cattle tested. Toxoplasma was detected in two out of 35 samples from sheep, and in one out of 25 samples from goats tested but not in two bovine samples tested.
3. Additional information

The results are published in the Zoonosis Brochure 2017.

28. General evaluation: *Trichinella* spp.

1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years. In 2016, 2 human cases of unknown origin were notified.

2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans

In 2017, three human cases of laboratory confirmed trichinellosis were notified to the EMS. According to the information available, one case shall have acquired the infection abroad, one case in Austria and for one case the place of infection is unknown. In 2017, no cases in animals that were used for food production, farmed or wild, were detected In Austria.

3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union

Reconsider the necessity of routine *Trichinella* meat inspection in pig carcasses

4. Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

29. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Horses and *Trichinella* spp.

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent post, mortem monitoring scheme.

2. Measures in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended. Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended), Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended).

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In 2017, 546 slaughtered horses were examined, no infestation was detected.
5. Additional information
If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

30. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Wild boars and <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system
<p>Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about <i>Trichinella</i> investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.</p> <p>For diagnosis according to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion has been used.</p>
2. Measures in place
According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended. Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended), Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended).
3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority
According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.
4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In 2017, no case of <i>Trichinella</i> was found neither in farmed (1,544 animals examined) nor in wild wild boars (22,769 animals examined).
5. Additional information
If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

31. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Pigs and *Trichinella* spp.

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent post-mortem monitoring scheme.

For diagnosis according to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion has been used.

2. Measures in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended. Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended), Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended).

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2017, no case of *Trichinella* was found in farmed pigs (5,124,007 animals examined).

5. Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

32. General evaluation: Bovine tuberculosis

<p>1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country</p> <p>Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free. In humans the number of tuberculosis cases has been decreasing until 2015; since then, due to migration to Austria an increase has been observed. Cases of <i>M. bovis</i> or <i>M. caprae</i> are very seldom and reactivations of past infections. In 2017, in humans one <i>M. caprae</i> and one <i>M. bovis</i> case were confirmed. The <i>M. caprae</i> case did not show the same molecular typing patterns as the <i>M. caprae</i> isolated from wild red deer and cattle.</p>
<p>2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans</p> <p>Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. In 2008 the first case of <i>M. caprae</i> in a bovine animal was detected in the federal province of Tyrol. Since this time several studies carried out in the period of 2008 to 2013 and surveillance data show, that <i>M. caprae</i> is endemic in wild red deer in single areas (hot spots) of the both federal provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg. The spill over from red deer to pastured cattle during transhumance season is known. Therefore, after transhumance season, cattle of these regions are tested every year. Since then, every year a few bovines have been identified to be infected with <i>M. caprae</i>. In 2017, nine bovines out of 8 herds were diagnosed with <i>M. caprae</i>. In 2011 the Regulation on TB in red deer (Rotwild-TBC-Verordnung, BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011) has been implemented to control <i>M. caprae</i> in red deer. Bovines and goats kept together with bovines shall be tested (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) for TB in defined areas of risk (where TB in wild red deer is known) according to the Regulation on TB in cattle (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl. II Nr. 322/2008) and according to the epidemiological situation.</p>
<p>3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union</p> <p>Continuation of the existing control programs.</p>
<p>4. Additional information</p> <p>The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.</p>

33. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Other animals and *Mycobacterium* other than *M. bovis*

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

According to the federal law for zoonoses (BGBl. I no. 2005/128) following shall be subject to monitoring: tuberculosis caused by *M. bovis* according to the epidemiological situation.

According to federal law Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I no. 13/2016) and the Regulation Tierseuchen-Untersuchungspflicht-Verordnung BGBl. II no. 90/2007) all slaughter animals shall be subject to ante and post-mortem inspection. Samples from tuberculosis suspected animals are taken after slaughter. Tissues of slaughtered animals which are visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye and lymph nodes. The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to

<p>the NRL for tuberculosis in animals. Samples are examined by (I) staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material. (II) Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling. After decontamination of the homogenized sample material (2g homogenized add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (BD - Becton Dickinson: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37° C +/-1° C up to 12 weeks. If isolates are obtained, MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany). A case is defined according to the Regulation (EC) no 854/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E.</p>
<p>2. Measures in place</p>
<p>In case of positive findings, measures are taken according to the Regulation (EC) no 654/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E. Vaccination is prohibited in Austria.</p>
<p>3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority</p>
<p>The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.</p>
<p>4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection</p>
<p><i>M. bovis</i> or <i>M. caprae</i> was not detected in any animal tested.</p>
<p>5. Additional information</p>
<p>The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and the annual Veterinary Report.</p>

34. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Bovines and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

According to Council Directive 64/432/EEC from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free (OTF) Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. Therefore, as of May 2000 the nationwide intradermal testing has been suspended and the disease is now monitored as a part of ante- and post mortem inspection of all bovine animals and goats (which were kept together with bovines) slaughtered.

According to the national Regulation the "Rindertuberkuloseverordnung" (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all mycobacteria belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTC) are compulsory notifiable. The "Rindertuberkuloseverordnung" shall apply to bovine animals and to goats, which are kept together with bovine animals.

According to the monitoring system of ante and post mortem inspection of slaughtered animals, samples are taken from carcasses which show pathological-anatomical alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis

at slaughterhouse. Laboratory examination and diagnosis is done by the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Mödling).

The BMGF orders annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (where TB in wild red deer is known; special testing zones and special monitoring zones according to §1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl. II no. 322/2008 applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test) of the provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg after the end of transhumance season, subsequently to the detection of *M. caprae* positive cases in wild red deer.

After official announcement census testing carried out in specific risk areas including all animals older than 6 months (cattle and goats kept together with bovines) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

In specific risk areas bovine animals and goats are tested using the intradermal testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no.322/2008). A reactor is an animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive) to intradermal testing.

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture is performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for tuberculosis in animals in Mödling. After decontamination of the homogenized sample material (2g, homogenized, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (BD - Becton Dickinson: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37° C +/-1° C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany). Identification of Mycobacteria species and genotyping of isolates is undertaken using molecular biological methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), DNA-striptechnology, restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), spoligotyping and MIRU-VNTR (mycobacterial interspersed repetitive unit variable number tandem repeat) analysis.

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all live animals suspected being infected shall be killed for diagnostic purposes. All animals of the holding of origin of such animals must be tested immediately (simultaneous intradermal test) and epidemiologic investigations must be carried out. The status of disease freedom of the holding which is suspected of being infected is suspended and subsequently withdrawn in case of confirmation of the disease. The holding is banned immediately after suspicion. Milk from such holdings shall be used for human consumption only according to the specifications laid down in Annex III, Section IX, Chapter I of the Regulation EC No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 laying down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin or shall be used after boiling for feeding the animals of the affected holding only. The status freedom of disease of an infected holding is regained after culling of all animals that did not reveal a negative result and disinfection under official control.

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung tuberculosis is defined as an infection with mycobacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

If control programmes are approved by the EC a link to the specific programme of the Commission website can be provided

2. Measures in place

Subsequent to the detection of *M. caprae* positive wild red deer in specific areas of the provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg the BMASGK has ordered annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (special testing zones and special monitoring zones according to §1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

Vaccination is prohibited in Austria.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

The notification of bovine animals and goats kept together with bovines suspected of being infected is compulsory.
4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection
In 2017, in specific risk areas in the provinces of Tirol and Vorarlberg 17,699 bovine animals in 1,558 herds have been examined performing the simultaneous intradermal test. An infection with <i>M. caprae</i> was confirmed in nine bovines out of eight herds. <i>M. bovis</i> was not detected. In the course of post mortem meat examinations, no infection with Mycobacterium tuberculosis Complex could be detected. Austria kept the status officially free of bovine tuberculosis because 99.987 of all bovine herds (60,675) were free of bovine tuberculosis. In 1999, Austria achieved the status officially free of bovine tuberculosis and has kept that status since then. Due to the rigid control program of red deer that are proven as the reservoir for <i>M. caprae</i> in the eradication areas the number of infected bovines and herds could be reduced in the last year.
5. Additional information
<i>M. caprae</i> is differentiated in Austria. The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and the annual Veterinary Report.

35. General evaluation: Verocytotoxic <i>E. coli</i> (VTEC)
1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country
In 2016, the number of human VETC cases notified to EMS reached a new maximum of 177 cases (2.03 cases per 100,000 population) (EMS/NRL-VTEC as of January 19, 2017). That increase of cases is not due to an outbreak but due to the effect that the reimbursement for laboratory analysis of VTEC of suspected human samples has been modified; so more samples were analysed and also found positive for VTEC. The average incidence during the last five years (2011-2015) has been lower at 1.55 cases per 100,000 population.
2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans
In 2017, 250 laboratory confirmed VTEC-cases have been notified to the EMS. This increase that already could be observed in 2016 was due to fact that more patient samples have been tested for the presence of VTEC than in the previous years.
3. Any recent specific action in the Member State or suggested for the European Union
Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, pediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.
4. Additional information
If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

36. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: VTEC in foodstuffs

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Sampling scheme:

In 2017, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2017 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Probenplan und Berichtsschema 2017“ (BMGF-75500/0158-II/B/13/2016) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly, depending on their risk categorization. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). Sampling by the competent authority is distributed evenly throughout the year for scheduled samples: food of animal origin is focussed on. In 2017, the sampling plan intended approximately 23,500 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

Testing scheme:

VTEC is analyzed according to ISO/TS 13136. There is no further testing for negative PCR results in the bacterial enrichment. If the bacterial enrichment is PCR-positive, it is streaked on to solid media. At least 50 colonies are tested for the presence of *stx1* and/or *stx2*. The Shigatoxin producing *E. coli* is sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) (NRL-VTEC) in Graz where the presence of the *stx*-genes, *eae*-genes and additional virulence factors is assessed by PCR. Subsequently the VTEC is serotyped conventionally (antisera). All isolates detected in food have to be sent to the MRL-VTEC in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored.

2. Measures in place

No preventive measures in place

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

No notification system in place.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2017, in total 1,005 samples were tested for VTEC, 920 samples of animal origin, 50 samples of non-animal origin and 35 samples of other processed food products, prepared dishes (20 samples) and food for special nutritional uses (12 samples). In total 25 samples were positive for VTEC. One sample (milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption) out of 211 (0.5%, CI: 0-3%) samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cow's, sheep's or goat's milk) were positive for VTEC. No positive findings were made in dairy products, cheeses or any other milk. 212 samples of fresh meat of several animals (bovine animals, deer, pig, rabbit, sheep, wild boar) were tested for VTEC resulting in 14 positive samples (6.6%, CI: 4-11%), which is a comparable prevalence to 2015 (7.24%) and 2016 (7.5%, CI: 4-13%). The highest prevalence of VTEC was detected in fresh meat from venison in 23.5% (CI: 14-37%, in 12 out of 51 samples), comparable to 2016 (21.2% positivity rate in fresh meat samples from venison). No VTEC was detected in fresh sheep meat, pig meat, wild boar or

<p>wild game (bird) (43 tested samples). 371 samples of meat products and meat preparations (38) of several animals were tested for VTEC showing 7 positive samples (1.9%, CI:1-4%), which is lower than in 2015 (4.2%, CI:3-7%) and 2016 (2.2%, CI: 1-5%). VTEC could not be detected in any food of non-animal origin (including all processed food, etc.). The distribution of serotypes did not reveal any peaks or a clustering for any specific type: in food each serotype was detected only once or twice. The total number of samples, tested for VTEC, has increased from 2013 (776) to 2016 (1,346) and lowered to 1,005 samples in 2017. In each year different food categories show a peak in their positivity rate. Overall no trend is observable in the Austrian data-set for VTEC in any food-category within the last five years.</p>
<p>5. Additional information</p>
<p>The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.</p>

<p>37. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Animals and VTEC</p>
<p>1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system</p>
<p>In 2016, the monitoring of VTEC in animals has been ceased due to the high costs of the monitoring and lack of EU-co-financing. The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was stopped after 11 years in 2015.</p>

<p>38. General evaluation: <i>Yersinia</i> spp.</p>
<p>1. History of the disease and/or infection in the country</p>
<p>Yersiniosis is not considered a major food-borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis and has been stable over the last years.</p>
<p>2. Evaluation of status, trends and relevance as a source for humans</p>
<p>In 2017, 95 human cases were notified to the EMS, 91 cases of <i>Y. enterocolitica</i> and one case of <i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i> were confirmed by the NRC-Yersiniosis. The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.</p>
<p>3. Additional information</p>
<p>If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.</p>

<p>39. Description of Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system: Animals</p>

and *Yersinia* spp.

1. Monitoring/Surveillance/Control programmes system

Not relevant in Austria therefore no program has been performed so far.

2. Measures in place

No measures foreseen.

3. Notification system in place to the national competent authority

Yersinia in animals is not notifiable.

4. Results of investigations and national evaluation of the situation, the trends and sources of infection

No results available.

5. Additional information

Not applicable.

40. Food-borne Outbreaks

1. System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food-borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (n = 95) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, the investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province, that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food-borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

2. Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting

The large majority of food-borne outbreaks (71 %) have been classified as household outbreaks because in most cases it has not been possible to merge different household outbreaks by identifying unique foodstuffs that human cases from different households consumed. Better coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - could decrease the total

number of outbreaks.

3. National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country

Trends in numbers of outbreaks and numbers of human cases involved

In 2017, 69 food-borne outbreaks affecting 227 persons were reported. 56 persons were hospitalized and two lethal cases occurred. The total number of food-borne outbreaks decreased by 13.8 % compared to 2016. The average number of cases affected by an outbreak was 3.3 persons, ranging from two to 17 persons per outbreak. 7 % (14 % in 2016, 18 % in 2015, 13.5 % in 2014, 16 % in 2013, and 14 % in 2012) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 38 % of all food-borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n = 24), 45 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n = 29) and 66 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n = 19) compared to 60 % in 2016.

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 81 % of all food borne outbreaks (95 % in 2016, 85 % in 2015, 91 % in 2014, 77 % in 2013, and 93 % in 2012). Nine outbreaks (13 %) were reported as outbreaks with strong evidence. The following food items have been associated with strong evidence to outbreaks: eggs and egg products (3 outbreaks), one outbreak each by buffet meals, cheese, meat and meat products, pig meat and products thereof, vegetables and juices and other products thereof and fish and fish products. For the majority of outbreaks (weak evidence outbreaks), the data quality does not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

At the present, the data quality does not allow conclusions on the relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

In 2017, 24.7 % (15.6 % in 2016, 25.8 % in 2015, 15.3 % in 2014; 19 % in 2013; 17.3 % in 2012) of patients affected by these food-borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized; two died in association with an outbreak.

4. Descriptions of single outbreaks of special interest

Kornschober C. (2018): Nationale Referenzzentrale für Salmonellen - Jahresbericht 2017. Mitteilungen des öffentlichen Gesundheitswesens - Public Health Newsletter 1. Quartal 2018. (http://bmg.cms.apa.at/cms/home/attachments/6/3/5/CH1692/CMS1520340978009/jahresbericht_salmonellen_2017.pdf, last access: 12.05.2018)

Kornschober C and Pekard-Amenitsch S. (2018): Nationale Referenzzentrale für Botulismus - Jahresbericht 2017. Mitteilungen des öffentlichen Gesundheitswesens - Public Health Newsletter 1. Quartal 2018. (http://bmg.cms.apa.at/cms/home/attachments/3/0/6/CH1692/CMS1520340270474/jahresbericht_botulismus_2017.pdf, last access: 12.05.2018)

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (2018): Multi-country outbreak of *Listeria monocytogenes* serogroup IVb, multi-locus sequence type 6, infections probably linked to frozen corn, 22 March 2018. Stockholm and Parma; 2018. Available from: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/search?s=Multi-country+outbreak+of+Listeria+monocytogenes+serogroup+IVb%2C+multi-locus+sequence+type+6%2C+infections+probably+linked+to+froze>

5. Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

6. Any specific action decided in the Member State or suggested for the European Union as a whole on the basis of the recent/current situation

Since the amendment of the Austrian Food Safety and Consumer Protection Law (LMSVG) in 2010, health authorities are allowed to order market withdrawals and to recall products even without microbiological proof, they can decide on control measures already due to strong epidemiological evidence on the disease's origin, spread, and development. In case of a food-borne outbreak relating to more than one MS it is important to coordinate the reporting in these MSs in order to count this outbreak Europe-wide only one time.

7. Additional information

The situation of food-borne outbreaks is published in the National Zoonoses Brochure each year.

41. Institutions and laboratories involved in antimicrobial resistance monitoring and reporting

Central Veterinary Services of the former Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF), now Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection:

The Central Veterinary Services assigned the AGES to perform the AMR monitoring program.

AGES, Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR):

Sampling plans, analyses of laboratory results and reports are prepared by the AGES DSR

Officially authorized Veterinarians:

The officially authorized Veterinarians do the sampling at slaughterhouses and take care that samples are transported according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing E. coli from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

Food inspectors:

Food inspectors do the sampling at retail and take care that samples are transported according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing E. coli from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) at the Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), AGES Graz:

At the VEMI all caecal samples from slaughterhouses are processed and examined for indicator E. coli, beta-lactamase producing E. coli and carbapenemase producing E. coli. VEMI provides data to DSR for data analysis and reporting.

Official Food Control Laboratory (ILMU) at the Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), AGES Graz:

All food samples according to the CID 2013/652/EU are examined at the ILMU Graz. ILMU provides data to DSR for data analysis and reporting.

National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AR), Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), AGES Graz:

All indicator E. coli and (presumptive) beta-lactamase producing E. coli are susceptibility tested in the NRL-AR. NRL provides data to DSR for data analysis and reporting.

National Reference Centre for Salmonella (NRC-S) at Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), AGES Graz:

All salmonella are typed and susceptibility tested in the NRC-S. NRC provides data to DSR for data analysis and reporting.

42. General Antimicrobial Resistance Evaluation

1. Situation and epidemiological evolution (trends and sources) regarding AMR to critically important antimicrobials (CIAs) over time until recent situation

Indicator E. coli

Resistance monitoring of bacteria isolated from caeca from different slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004. The microdilution method applying ECOFFs was used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of all isolates. In 2014, the new legislation (CID 2013/652/EU) was implemented in Austria. In 2004, the percentage of indicator E. coli susceptible to all antimicrobials tested was similar for isolates from broilers and fattening pigs (27% and 28%) but much higher for bovine (all age groups) isolates (91%). In the following years, the percentage of fully susceptible isolates from broilers varied, reaching the lowest rate in 2010 (10.5%); since then, the percentage of fully susceptible isolates has increased, reaching 21% in 2014 and 33.5% in 2016. From 2004 to 2013, the percentage of fully susceptible isolates from pigs stayed more or less the same, and in 2015 the highest rate was reached, with 48% fully susceptible isolates. In isolates from bovines, no significant variations have been observed. Indicator E. coli from turkeys were examined for the first time in 2014. Compared with 2014, an increase of fully susceptible isolates could be observed from 33.6% to 42.2% in 2016.

In 2015, high resistance rates in isolates from pigs were detected towards tetracyclines (47%) and sulphonamides (23%), moderate rates towards ampicillin (13%) and trimethoprim (10%).

Resistance rates to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, chloramphenicol, cefotaxime, ceftazidime and gentamicin were low (4.9%, 3.1%, 3.7%, 2.5%, 1.8%, and 2.5%). One isolate showed resistance to colistin (0.6%); no resistance was found towards meropenem, tigecycline and azithromycin.

Four of the indicator E. coli-isolates were resistant to 3rd generation cephalosporins. Those isolates were tested in the panel 2. Three isolates were confirmed as ESBL-producing E. coli, one was finally assessed sensitive to 3rd generation cephalosporins.

beta-lactamase producing E. coli

Specific Monitoring of Beta-Lactamase producing E. coli in samples from animals and food has been started in 2015 in accordance with CID 2013/652/EU. Previously, single projects were carried out, eg. in 2012 and in 2013 the AGES conducted projects with food samples collected in one Austrian province. In 2012, 50 samples of fresh broiler meat from conventional and 50 from organic production, as well as 54 samples of fresh turkey meat from conventional and 44 samples from organic production were selective tested for carbapenemase-producing-, ESBL-producing -, and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacteriaceae. Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae were not be detected in any food sample. ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae were found in 30 (60%) of conventional and in 46 (92%) organic broiler meat samples, in 9 (17%) of conventional and 3 (7%) of organic turkey meat samples. Ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacteriaceae were isolated from 48 (96%) of both each, conventional and organic broiler meat samples, and from 51 (94%) of conventional and 43 (98%) of organic turkey meat samples. These isolates showed high co-resistances to ampicillin, tetracyclines and sulfonamides.

In 2013, 100 samples of each pork, beef, and eggs (50 samples each of conventional and organic production) were selective tested for tested for carbapenemase-producing-, ESBL-producing -,

ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacteriaceae, and MRSA. Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae could not be detected in any food sample. ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae were found in 6% of conventional and 18% of organic pork meat samples, in 18% of conventional and 6% of organic beef samples, but in none of the tested eggs. Ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacteriaceae were isolated from 22% of conventional and 14% of organic pork meat samples, from 30% of conventional and 4% of organic beef samples, but in none of the examined eggs. MRSA was detected in five conventional and one organic pork meat samples, in seven conventional and four organic beef samples, but was not detected in any eggs sampled.

2015: Out of 257 caecals samples from pigs tested, 134 suspected ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were identified and susceptibility tested. 117 isolates showed resistance to both 3rd generation cephalosporins, 17 were resistant only against cefotaxime. 124 isolates were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*, 10 isolates as AmpC-producing *E. coli*. Out of 247 caecal samples from pigs, carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any sample.

Pork: Out of 224 samples, 22 suspected Enzyme-producing *E. coli* were isolated. In total, 19 ESBL-producing and one AmpC-producing *E. coli* were confirmed. 216 samples of fresh pig meat were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh pig meat sample.

Beef: In 7 out of 234 samples suspected Enzyme-producing *E. coli* were detected, all seven were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*. 226 samples of fresh beef were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

2016: Broiler meat samples: Three-hundred fresh broiler meat samples were tested, 191 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (63.7%) were detected and confirmed. Out of 191 isolates tested, 29 (15.2%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Very high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (61.8%), and high resistance rates to quinolones (47.6%), to tetracycline (37.7 %), and to trimethoprim (35.1%). Resistance to colistin was detected in one isolate; the mobile plasmid mediated *mcr-1*-gene was confirmed. Multiple resistances were found in 84.8% of the tested isolates. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Broiler caecal samples: Of 306 samples tested, 160 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (52.3%) were confirmed as enzyme-producing *E. coli*. Twenty-eight isolates (17.5%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Very high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (60.0%), to quinolones (58.1%), and to tetracycline (53.1 %). Resistance to colistin was detected in one isolate; the mobile plasmid mediated *mcr-1*-gene was confirmed. Multiple resistances were found in 82.5% of the tested isolates. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Turkey caecal samples: One-hundred and eighty-three samplers were tested, 81 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were detected and 80 (43.7%) of these confirmed as ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. Eleven isolates (13.8%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Extremely high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (77.5%), to tetracycline (76.3 %), and very high rates to quinolones (56.3%). Resistance to colistin was not detected. Multiple resistances were found in 85.2% of the tested isolates. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Carbapenemase producing *E. coli*

Specific Monitoring of carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* in samples from animals and food has been started in 2015 in accordance with CID 2013/652/EU. Previously, single projects were carried out, eg. in 2012 and in 2013 the AGES conducted projects with food samples collected in one Austrian province. In 2012, 50 samples of fresh broiler meat from conventional and 50 from organic production, as well as 54 samples of fresh turkey meat from conventional and 44 samples from organic production were selective tested for carbapenemase-producing-, ESBL-producing -, and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacteriaceae. Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae were not be detected in any food sample.

In 2013, 100 samples of each pork, beef, and eggs (50 samples each of conventional and organic production) were selective tested for tested for carbapenemase-producing-, ESBL-producing -, Ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacteriaceae, and MRSA. Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae could not be detected in any food sample.

In 2015, out of 247 caecal samples from pigs, carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any sample.

Pork: 216 samples of fresh pig meat were analysed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh pig meat sample.

Beef: 226 samples of fresh beef were tested on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

2016: Broiler meat samples: Three-hundred fresh broiler meat samples were tested, carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Broiler caecal samples: Of 306 samples tested, carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Turkey caecal samples: One-hundred and eighty-three samplers were tested; carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Salmonella spp.

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from different slaughtered animals has been started in Austria in 2004. Since 2007, the monitoring of AMR in *Salmonella* from poultry (obtained from national control program) has been performed according to Commission Decision 2007/407/EC. The microdilution method applying ECOFFs was used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of poultry-isolates. In 2014, the new legislation (CID 2013/652/EU) was implemented in Austria and also the testing of isolates from slaughterhouses in accordance with Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005.

All human *Salmonella*-isolates have to be sent to the NRC-S for typing and AST. AST of all human isolates are performed in the disk diffusion tests using EUCAST-clinical breakpoints.

2. Public health relevance of the findings on food-borne AMR in animals and foodstuffs

Indicator *E. coli*

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans. It cannot be excluded that resistant bacteria or resistance genes are transmitted to humans after animal contact or via food from those animals.

beta-lactamase producing *E. coli*

It cannot be excluded that resistant bacteria or resistance genes are transmitted to humans after animal contact or via food from those animals. So hygiene standards after animal contact should be kept very high and also in kitchen (hand hygiene, cross contamination, thoroughly cooking of possible risky food).

Carbapenemase producing *E. coli*

So far no findings of carbapenemase producing *E. coli* in food or animal samples in Austria.

Salmonella spp.

In 2015, on carcasses of pigs *Salmonella* were not detected in course of the process controls, so no susceptibility tests have been performed. Isolates of carcasses of bovines under 1 year have not been collected. Results concerning isolates from poultry have been reported and described in the Report 2016.

3. Recent actions taken to control AMR in food producing animals and food

beta-lactamase producing *E. coli*

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Carbapenemase producing *E. coli*

No actions so far.

Salmonella spp.

No actions needed.

4. Any specific action decided in the Member State or suggestions to the European Union for

actions to be taken against food-borne AMR threat
Continuation of the co-financed programme. Salmonella spp. No actions needed.
5. Additional information
Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

43. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Indicator <i>E. coli</i> in fattening pigs
1. General description of sampling design and strategy
The preparation of the sampling systems (for indicator <i>E. coli</i> and ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>E. coli</i>) is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator- <i>E. coli</i> is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for ESBL/AmpC - producing <i>E. coli</i> was given). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample (190 of all samples collected were tested for indicator <i>E. coli</i>).
2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category
The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 17 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all fattened and slaughtered pigs in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing <i>E. coli</i> (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing <i>E. coli</i>). To save resources, as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample, therefore, 190 of these samples were also tested for the indicator <i>E. coli</i> . In recent years, <i>E. coli</i> were isolated from 96% of caeca of pigs. To ensure that 170 isolates are obtained – caeca were only analysed in the lab when the sampled animal originated from a holding that was not sampled before - a sample size of 190 samples was calculated. For stratification procedures the numbers of slaughtered Austrian pigs per abattoir in 2016 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used (first isolated indicator- <i>E. coli</i> or first enzyme-producing <i>E. coli</i>). Samples from 208 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 9 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range (> 2 ° C and < 8 ° C). If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 18 samples had to be discarded because the caeca originated from fattening pigs' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year. From the remaining 181 samples, 180 isolates of indicator <i>E. coli</i> were obtained.

<p>3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category</p> <p>Using a random number generator the day of slaughter was selected when the sampling should be performed, e. g. during one month 7 pigs had to be sampled on abattoir X: At the end of the previous month the sampler had to assess the number of slaughter days in abattoir X, e.g. 15. All Fridays and Thursdays if sample delivery in the lab could not be ensured until Friday, 9:00, were subtracted, e.g. 15-5=10 days remaining. Seven numbers out of 1-15 were random generated using Microsoft Excel or https://rechneronline.de/zufallszahlen/ giving the day when a pig had to be sampled (e.g. day 1, 3, 6, 8, 8, 9, 10). The procedure of the selection of the animal that had to be sampled was similar: Generating a number out of all animals slaughtered on a day selected above, the number of the animal that had to be sampled was given. If two pigs had to be sampled on one day, a second number had to be created (#2). Before sampling the second pigs on the same day it had to be assured that the second animal originated from another holding than #1. If one of the selected animals had not been raised in an Austrian holding the first Austrian pig following in the line had to be sampled.</p>
<p>4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation</p> <p>The intestinal contents are streaked onto MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Two suspect E. coli colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (COS, Biomerieux) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of E. coli was performed using MALDI-TOFF (PV 7228) double tested; if no E. coli could be identified, the second isolate was tested.</p>
<p>5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance</p> <p>NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).</p>
<p>6. Results of investigation</p> <p>In the NRL AR 180 isolates of indicator E. coli were susceptibility tested. 90 isolates (50%) were fully susceptible to all antimicrobials tested. Resistance was found towards Tetracycline (73 isolates, 40.6%), Sulfonamides (44 isolates, 24.4%), Ampicillin (36 isolates, 20.0%), Trimethoprim (23 isolates, 12.8%), Ciprofloxacin (7 isolates, 3.9%), Chloramphenicol (6 isolates, 3.3%), Nalidixic Acid (5 isolates, 2.8%), Cefotaxime (4 isolates, 2.2%) Gentamicin und Ceftazidime (3 isolates each, 1.7%) and Azithromycin (1 isolate, 0.6%). Four presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing E. coli isolates with resistance to 3rd generation cephalosporins were analysed in panel 2. Two isolates were identified as ESBL-, one as AmpC-producing E. coli; the fourth isolate was confirmed sensitive to 3rd generation cephalosporins (MIC=0.25 mg/l Cefotaxime). Colistin resistance was not detected in any isolate.</p>
<p>7. Additional information</p> <p>Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).</p>

44. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Indicator *E. coli* in bovines < 1 year

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In Austria, the production of meat of bovines under one year of age is less than 10 000 tonnes slaughtered per year. Although Austria decided to sample and test on a voluntary basis also bovines slaughtered under one year of age for indicator *E. coli* and ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. The preparation of the sampling systems (for indicator *E. coli* and ESBL/AmpC-producing *E. coli*) is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator-*E. coli* is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was given by legislation). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample (190 of all samples collected were tested for indicator *E. coli*).

2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category

The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 24 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all bovines under one year of age in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing *E. coli* (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing *E. coli*). To save resources, as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample, therefore, 190 of these samples were also tested for the indicator *E. coli*. To ensure that 170 isolates are obtained – caeca were only analyzed in the lab when the sampled animal originated from a holding that was not sampled before - a sample size of 190 samples was calculated.

For stratification procedures the numbers of slaughtered Austrian bovines under one year per abattoir in 2016 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used (first isolated indicator-*E. coli* or first sample for ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*).

Samples from 210 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 8 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range (> 2 ° C and < 8 ° C) and 7 samples were gathered from bovines older than 1 year . If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 11 samples had to be discarded because the caeca originated from bovines' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year. From the remaining 184 samples, 181 isolates of indicator *E. coli* were obtained.

3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category

Using a random number generator the day of slaughter was selected when the sampling should be performed, e. g. during one month 7 bovines under one year have to be sampled on abattoir X: At the end of the previous month the sampler had to assess the number of slaughter days in abattoir X, e.g. 15. All Fridays and Thursdays if sample delivery in the lab could not be ensured until Friday, 9:00, were subtracted, e.g. 15-5=10 days remaining. Seven numbers out of 1-10 are random generated using Microsoft Excel or <https://rechneronline.de/zufallszahlen/> giving the day when a pig had to be sampled (e.g. day 1, 3, 6, 8, 8, 9, 10). The procedure of the selection of the animal that had to be sampled was similar: Generating a number out of all animals slaughtered on a day selected above, the number of the animal that had to be sampled was given. If two bovines had to be sampled on one day, a second number had to be created (#2). Before sampling the second bovine on the same day it had to be assured that the second animal originated from another holding than #1. If one of the selected animals had not been

<p>raised in an Austrian holding the first Austrian bovine under one year following in the line had to be sampled.</p>
<p>4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation</p>
<p>The intestinal contents are streaked onto MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Two suspect <i>E. coli</i> colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (COS, Biomerieux) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of <i>E. coli</i> was performed using MALDI-TOF (PV 7228) double tested; if no <i>E. coli</i> could be identified, the second isolate was tested.</p>
<p>5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance</p>
<p>NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).</p>
<p>6. Results of investigation</p>
<p>In the NRL AR 181 isolates of indicator <i>E. coli</i> were susceptibility tested. 131 isolates (72.4%) were fully susceptible to all antimicrobials tested. Resistance was found towards Tetracycline (44 isolates, 24.3%), Sulfonamides (32 isolates, 17.7%), Ampicillin (16 isolates, 8.8%), Trimethoprim (13 isolates, 7.2%), Chloramphenicol (11 isolates, 6.0%), Ciprofloxacin (7 isolates, 3.9%), Nalidixic Acid (5 isolates, 2.8%), Cefotaxime (4 isolates, 2.2%) and Gentamicin (1 isolate, 0.6%). Four presumptive ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>E. coli</i> isolates with resistances to 3rd generation Cephalosporins were analysed in panel 2, although no ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>E. coli</i> was confirmed. Two isolates were resistant to 3rd generation Cephalosporins and the synergy test was positive (only with Cefotaxime) but the confirmed MIC was 0.5 mg/L Cefotaxim. The third isolate did not show resistance to 3rd generation Cephalosporins and the fourth isolate was resistant only to Ceftazidime. Colistin resistance was not detected in any isolate.</p>
<p>7. Additional information</p>
<p>Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).</p>

<p>45. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>E. coli</i> in fattening pigs</p>
<p>1. General description of sampling design and strategy</p>
<p>The preparation of the sampling systems (for indicator <i>E. coli</i> and ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>E. coli</i>) is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator-<i>E. coli</i> is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>E. coli</i> was given). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample.</p>
<p>2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category</p>

The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 17 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all fattened and slaughtered pigs in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing *E. coli* (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing *E. coli*). To ensure that valid samples from 300 epidemiological units are analysed – caeca were only analysed in the lab (I) when the sampled animal originated from a holding that was not sampled before, (II) the temperature of the sample was according to the protocol and (III) expiry date was not passed - a sample size of 330 samples was calculated.

For stratification procedures the numbers of slaughtered Austrian pigs per abattoir in 2016 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used (first isolated indicator-*E. coli* or first enzyme-producing *E. coli*).

Samples from 341 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 50 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range (> 2 ° C and < 8 ° C). If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 33 samples had to be discarded because the caeca originated from fattening pigs' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year (up to 5 animals sampled from originating from one holding). From the remaining 291 samples, 181 presumptive ESBL/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were obtained.

3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category

Using a random number generator the day of slaughter was selected when the sampling should be performed, e. g. during one month 7 pigs had to be sampled on abattoir X: At the end of the previous month the sampler had to assess the number of slaughter days in abattoir X, e.g. 15. All Fridays and Thursdays if sample delivery in the lab could not be ensured until Friday, 9:00, were subtracted, e.g. 15-5=10 days remaining. Seven numbers out of 1-10 were random generated using Microsoft Excel or <https://rechneronline.de/zufallszahlen/> giving the day when a pig had to be sampled (e.g. day 1, 3, 6, 8, 8, 9, 10). The procedure of the selection of the animal that had to be sampled was similar: Generating a number out of all animals slaughtered on a day selected above, the number of the animal that had to be sampled was given. If two pigs had to be sampled on one day, a second number had to be created (#2). Before sampling the second pigs on the same day it had to be assured that the second animal originated from another holding than #1. If one of the selected animals had not been raised in an Austrian holding the first Austrian pig following in the line had to be sampled.

4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation

The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

6. Results of investigation

181 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (62.2%) were isolated and susceptibility tested in the NRL-AR using panel 1 and 2. All isolated were resistant to Cefotaxime (and Ampicillin), 178 also to

Ceftazidime. 111 isolates showed resistances towards Sulfonamides (61.3 %), 104 towards Tetracycline (57.5 %), 103 towards Trimethoprim (56.9 %), 42 towards Ciprofloxacin (23.2 %), 35 towards Nalidixic acid (19.3 %), 16 towards Chloramphenicol (8.8 %), 5 towards Gentamicin (2.8 %) und 4 towards Azithromycin (2.2 %). No resistance was detected towards Colistin.

171 isolates (58.8% of all pigs samples) showed a positive synergy test (eight isolates not with Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid) and could be confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*, ten isolates (negative synergy test and resistance to Cefoxitin, 3.4%) were identified as AmpC-producing *E. coli*.

7. Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

46. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: ESBL/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in bovines under one year of age

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In Austria, the production of meat of bovines under one year of age is less than 10 000 tonnes slaughtered per year. Although Austria decided to sample and test on a voluntary basis also bovines slaughtered under one year of age for indicator *E. coli* and ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. The preparation of the sampling systems (for indicator *E. coli* and ESBL/AmpC-producing *E. coli*) is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator-*E. coli* is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was given by legislation). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample.

2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category

The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 24 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all bovines under one year in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing *E. coli* (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing *E. coli*). To ensure that valid samples from 300 epidemiological units are analysed – caeca were only analysed in the lab (I) when the sampled animal originated from a holding that was not sampled before, (II) the temperature of the sample was according to the protocol and (III) expiry date was not passed - a sample size of 330 samples was calculated.

For stratification procedures the numbers of slaughtered Austrian bovines under one year per abattoir in 2016 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used (first isolated indicator-*E. coli* or first enzyme-producing *E. coli*).

Samples from 346 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 43 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range (> 2 ° C and < 8 ° C) or the sampled bovine was older than one year. If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 20 samples had to be discarded because the caeca originated from bovines' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year. From the remaining 303 samples, 68 presumptive ESBL/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (22.4%) were obtained.

<p>3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category</p> <p>Using a random number generator the day of slaughter was selected when the sampling should be performed, e. g. during one month 7 pigs had to be sampled on abattoir X: At the end of the previous month the sampler had to assess the number of slaughter days in abattoir X, e.g. 15. All Fridays and Thursdays if sample delivery in the lab could not be ensured until Friday, 9:00, were subtracted, e.g. 15-5=10 days remaining. Seven numbers out of 1-15 were random generated using Microsoft Excel or https://rechneronline.de/zufallszahlen/ giving the day when a pig had to be sampled (e.g. day 1, 3, 6, 8, 8, 9, 10). The procedure of the selection of the animal that had to be sampled was similar: Generating a number out of all animals slaughtered on a day selected above, the number of the animal that had to be sampled was given. If two pigs had to be sampled on one day, a second number had to be created (#2). Before sampling the second pigs on the same day it had to be assured that the second animal originated from another holding than #1. If one of the selected animals had not been raised in an Austrian holding the first Austrian pig following in the line had to be sampled.</p>
<p>4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation</p> <p>The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing E. coli from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.</p>
<p>5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance</p> <p>NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).</p>
<p>6. Results of investigation</p> <p>68 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing E. coli (22.4%) were isolated and susceptibility tested in the NRL-AR using panel 1 and 2. All isolated were resistant to Cefotaxime (and Ampicillin), 67 also to Ceftazidime. 43 isolates showed resistances towards Sulfonamides (63.2 %), 41 towards Tetracycline (60.3 %), 36 towards Trimethoprim (52.9 %), 30 towards Ciprofloxacin (44.1 %), 18 towards Nalidixic acid (26.5 %), 12 towards Chloramphenicol (17.6 %), 7 towards Gentamicin (10.3 %) und 4 towards Azithromycin (5.9 %). No resistance was detected towards Colistin. 62 isolates (20.5% of all bovine samples) showed a positive synergy test (one isolates not with Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid) and were confirmed as ESBL-producing E. coli, 6 isolates (negative synergy test and resistance to Cefoxitin, 1.9%) were identified as AmpC-producing E. coli.</p>
<p>7. Additional information</p> <p>Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).</p>

47. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: ESBL/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in meat from pigs

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In 2017, fresh meat samples from pigs were collected according to the national campaign SPA A-800-17.

It was planned to gather 350 samples at retail (to exclude samples from identical batches, samples that arrived in the laboratory outside the temperature range of 5°C+/- 3°C or after the expiry date). The samples were distributed to the nine provinces proportional to the number of population including the number of overnight stays. The sampling was allocated to one month for smaller provinces and to two months for larger provinces. The sampling was performed by the food inspectors.

2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category

The food inspectors had to gather between 12 and 72 samples per province, from Monday to Wednesday. Up to 36 samples were collected in one month, if more samples were foreseen a second month was allocated. The sampling had to be distributed to all NUTS-3 regions per province and had to be sent within two days to the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology (IMED) in Graz. 349 samples of fresh pig meat were gathered and sent to the laboratory, 309 arrived correct in the laboratory and could be analyzed.

3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category

See chapter 1 and 2.

4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation

The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing E. coli from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

6. Results of investigation

Out of 309 samples 32 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producers (10.4%) were obtained and susceptibility tested in the NRL-AR using panel 1 and 2. All isolated were resistant to Cefotaxime (and Ampicillin), 31 also to Ceftazidime. Highest resistance rates were found towards Sulfonamides (71.9%), Trimethoprim (56.2 %) and Tetracycline (53.1 %). Resistances were also detected towards (Fluor-) Quinolones (21.9%), Chloramphenicol (15.6%), Azithromycin (6.2%) und Gentamicin (3.1%) but not towards Colistin. Twenty-eight isolates (87.5%) were multiresistant.

Twenty-nine isolates showed a positive synergy test (Ceftotaxime/Clavulanic acid and/or Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid), 27 (8.7% of all pig meat samples) were confirmed as ESBL- and two (0.6% showing a MIC to Cefoxitin > 8 mg/L) as ESBL+AmpC-producing E. coli. The three isolates with negative synergy test (1%) turned out to be AmpC-producers.

7. Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

producing *E. coli* in meat from bovines

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In 2017, fresh meat samples from bovines were collected according to the national campaign SPA A-800-17. It was planned to gather 350 samples at retail (to exclude samples from identical batches, samples that arrived in the laboratory outside the temperature range of 5°C+/- 3°C or after the expiry date). The samples were distributed to the nine provinces proportional to the number of population including the number of overnight stays. The sampling was allocated to one month for smaller provinces and to two months for larger provinces. The sampling was performed by the food inspectors.

2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category

The food inspectors had to gather between 12 and 72 samples per province, from Monday to Wednesday. Up to 36 samples were collected in one month, if more samples were foreseen a second month was allocated. The sampling had to be distributed to all NUTS-3 regions per province and had to be sent within two days to the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology (IMED) in Graz. 342 samples of fresh bovine meat were gathered and sent to the laboratory, 300 arrived correct in the laboratory and could be analyzed.

3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category

See chapter 1 and 2.

4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation

The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

6. Results of investigation

Out of 300 samples five presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producers (1.7%) were obtained and susceptibility tested in the NRL-AR using panel 1 and 2. All isolates were resistant to 3rd generation Cephalosporins (and Ampicillin). To isolates showed resistances to Sulfonamides, Trimethoprim und Tetracycline, one isolate to Sulfonamides and Trimethoprim and one to (Fluor-) Quinolones and Tetracycline. No resistance was detected towards Colistin. Four of the five isolates were multiresistant. All five isolates showed a positive synergy test (Ceftotaxime/Clavulanic acid and/or Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid) and were confirmed as ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

7. Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

49. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* in fattening pigs

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

The preparation of the sampling systems is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator-*E. coli* is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for carbapenemase -producing *E. coli* was given). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample.

2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category

The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 17 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all fattened and slaughtered pigs in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing *E. coli* (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing *E. coli*). To ensure that valid samples from 300 epidemiological units are analysed – caeca were only analysed in the lab (I) when the sampled animal originated from a holding that was not sampled before, (II) the temperature of the sample was according to the protocol and (III) expiry date was not passed - a sample size of 330 samples was calculated.

For stratification procedures the numbers of slaughtered Austrian pigs per abattoir in 2016 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used.

Samples from 341 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 50 could not be investigated because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range (> 2 ° C and < 8 ° C). If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 33 samples had to be discarded because the caeca originated from fattening pigs' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year (up to 5 animals sampled from originating from one holding). Finally, 283 samples were tested.

3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category

Using a random number generator the day of slaughter was selected when the sampling should be performed, e. g. during one month 7 pigs had to be sampled on abattoir X: At the end of the previous month the sampler had to assess the number of slaughter days in abattoir X, e.g. 15. All Fridays and Thursdays if sample delivery in the lab could not be ensured until Friday, 9:00, were subtracted, e.g. 15-5=10 days remaining. Seven numbers out of 1-10 were random generated using Microsoft Excel or <https://rechneronline.de/zufallszahlen/> giving the day when a pig had to be sampled (e.g. day 1, 3, 6, 8, 8, 9, 10). The procedure of the selection of the animal that had to be sampled was similar: Generating a number out of all animals slaughtered on a day selected above, the number of the animal that had to be sampled was given. If two pigs had to be sampled on one day, a second number had to be created (#2). Before sampling the second pigs on the same day it had to be assured that the second animal originated from another holding than #1. If one of the selected animals had not been raised in an Austrian holding the first Austrian pig following in the line had to be sampled.

4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation

The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance
NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).
6. Results of investigation
No carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> was detected.
7. Additional information
Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

50. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Carbapenemase –producing <i>E. coli</i> in bovines under one year of age
1. General description of sampling design and strategy
In Austria, the production of meat of bovines under one year of age is less than 10 000 tonnes slaughtered per year. Although Austria decided to sample and test on a voluntary basis also bovines slaughtered under one year of age for indicator <i>E. coli</i> and ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase–producing <i>E. coli</i> . The preparation of the sampling systems (for indicator <i>E. coli</i> and ESBL/AmpC–producing <i>E. coli</i>) is performed in two steps. In the first step the sample size for indicator- <i>E. coli</i> is calculated which guarantees a minimum of cost for a high reliability (the sample size of 300 caeca for ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> was given by legislation). In preparing the detailed sampling plans (second step) it is taken care to ensure that the samples taken constitute a representative cross-section over Austria, assuming an optimal temporal and geographical distribution of the samples taken. To save resources as many analyzes as possible were carried out per sample.
2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category
The caeca for the recovery of isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility testing was sampled at 24 slaughterhouses in which at least 60% of all bovines under one year in Austria are processed. All 300 samples had to be tested for enzyme-producing <i>E. coli</i> (ESBL-, AmpC- or carbapenemase producing <i>E. coli</i>). To ensure that valid samples from 300 epidemiological units are analysed – caeca were only analysed in the lab (I) when the sampled animal originated from a holding that was not sampled before, (II) the temperature of the sample was according to the protocol and (III) expiry date was not passed - a sample size of 330 samples was calculated. For stratification procedures the numbers of slaughtered Austrian bovines under one year per abattoir in 2016 were collected (data source: Veterinary information system, VIS). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. In the case that more than one animal has been sampled from the same epidemiological unit only the results of the first sampling of an epidemiological unit were used (first isolated indicator- <i>E. coli</i> or first enzyme-producing <i>E. coli</i>). Samples from 346 carcasses were sent to the laboratory for analysis, 43 could not be investigated

because they had arrived either after the expiry date in the laboratory or beyond the required temperature range (> 2 ° C and < 8 ° C) or the sampled bovine was older than one year. If caeca that could not be analyzed due to the given reasons additional carcasses had to be resampled at the same abattoir. 20 samples had to be discarded because the caeca originated from bovines' epidemiological units (holding) that were sampled already earlier throughout the year. Finally, 299 samples were tested for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*.

3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category

Using a random number generator the day of slaughter was selected when the sampling should be performed, e. g. during one month 7 pigs had to be sampled on abattoir X: At the end of the previous month the sampler had to assess the number of slaughter days in abattoir X, e.g. 15. All Fridays and Thursdays if sample delivery in the lab could not be ensured until Friday, 9:00, were subtracted, e.g. 15-5=10 days remaining. Seven numbers out of 1-10 were random generated using Microsoft Excel or <https://rechneronline.de/zufallszahlen/> giving the day when a pig had to be sampled (e.g. day 1, 3, 6, 8, 8, 9, 10). The procedure of the selection of the animal that had to be sampled was similar: Generating a number out of all animals slaughtered on a day selected above, the number of the animal that had to be sampled was given. If two pigs had to be sampled on one day, a second number had to be created (#2). Before sampling the second pigs on the same day it had to be assured that the second animal originated from another holding than #1. If one of the selected animals had not been raised in an Austrian holding the first Austrian pig following in the line had to be sampled.

4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation

The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.

5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

6. Results of investigation

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was detected.

7. Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

51. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Carbapenemase –producing *E. coli* in meat from pigs

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In 2017, fresh meat samples from pigs were collected according to the national campaign SPA A-800-17. It was planned to gather 350 samples at retail (to exclude samples from identical batches, samples that

<p>arrived in the laboratory outside the temperature range of 5°C+/- 3°C or after the expiry date). The samples were distributed to the nine provinces proportional to the number of population including the number of overnight stays. The sampling was allocated to one month for smaller provinces and to two months for larger provinces. The sampling was performed by the food inspectors.</p>
<p>2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category</p>
<p>The food inspectors had to gather between 12 and 72 samples per province, from Monday to Wednesday. Up to 36 samples were collected in one month, if more samples were foreseen a second month was allocated. The sampling had to be distributed to all NUTS-3 regions per province and had to be sent within two days to the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology (IMED) in Graz. 349 samples of fresh pig meat were gathered and sent to the laboratory, 309 arrived correct in the laboratory and 302 could be analyzed for carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i>.</p>
<p>3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category</p>
<p>See chapter 1 and 2.</p>
<p>4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation</p>
<p>The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.</p>
<p>5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance</p>
<p>NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).</p>
<p>6. Results of investigation</p>
<p>No carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> was detected.</p>
<p>7. Additional information</p>
<p>Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).</p>

52. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Carbapenemase –producing *E. coli* in meat from bovines

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In 2017, fresh meat samples from bovines were collected according to the national campaign SPA A-800-17. It was planned to gather 350 samples at retail (to exclude samples from identical batches, samples that arrived in the laboratory outside the temperature range of 5°C+/- 3°C or after the expiry date). The samples were distributed to the nine provinces proportional to the number of population including the number of overnight stays. The sampling was allocated to one month for smaller provinces and to two

months for larger provinces. The sampling was performed by the food inspectors.
2. Stratification procedure per animal population and food category
The food inspectors had to gather between 12 and 72 samples per province, from Monday to Wednesday. Up to 36 samples were collected in one month, if more samples were foreseen a second month was allocated. The sampling had to be distributed to all NUTS-3 regions per province and had to be sent within two days to the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology (IMED) in Graz. 342 samples of fresh bovine meat were gathered and sent to the laboratory, 300 arrived correct in the laboratory and 297 samples could be analyzed for carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> .
3. Randomisation procedure per animal population and food category
See chapter 1 and 2.
4. Analytical method used for detection and confirmation
The samples were analyzed according to the Laboratory Protocol "Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> from caecal samples" from January 2017, Version 4.
5. Laboratory methodology used for detection of antimicrobial resistance
NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and panel 2). Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).
6. Results of investigation
No carbapenemase-producing <i>E. coli</i> was detected.
7. Additional information
Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2017 (AURES 2017).

53. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Carcasses of fattening pigs, *Salmonella* spp.

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In 2017, on carcasses of pigs *Salmonella* were not detected in course of the process controls, so no susceptibility tests have been performed.

54. General Description of Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring: Carcasses of bovines under one year, *Salmonella* spp.

1. General description of sampling design and strategy

In 2017, on carcasses of bovines under one year Salmonella were not detected in course of the process controls, so no susceptibility tests have been performed.